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Special Issue – The Halifax River Urban Watershed

The colors of a Daytona postcard postmarked April 1966

Courtesy of Hyun Jung Cho, uploaded to Researchgate

Current Issue

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Special Issue, the Halifax River Urban Watershed

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Florida Geographer Readers:

The dust of the recent spring semester has settled, the summer rainy season is finally upon us, and issue 54 of the journal is now available. Bethune-Cookman University's Hyun Jung Cho and Michael A. Reiter approached me more than a year ago to explain that a host of scholars had been exploring the Halifax River watershed for couple of years, and they proposed to generate a collection of papers that elucidate selected aspects of the Halifax River region. It seemed to me that Florida's geographers would learn much from reading a wide-ranging series of essays about this popular but understudied part of the state; and now that these papers are here in final form, I suspect that you will learn much about the region as I did.

It is hard to pin the Halifax River down because it has no real beginning or end. It is part of the Intracoastal Waterway and most closely associated with Daytona and Volusia County, although one of its significant tributaries—Bulow Creek—originates in southern Flagler County. Other important tributaries include the Tomoka River and Spruce Creek. Physical geographers will appreciate that a series of gentle, north/south trending ridges in the region cause these tributaries to flow mostly *between* the ridges in a modified trellis drainage pattern, occasionally finding weak spots in a ridge through which they flow toward the Halifax. The northern end of the 20-something mile-long Halifax River is commonly understood to be that portion of the Intracoastal around the Volusia/Flagler County line. The southern end? You could define it as Ponce Inlet, just north of New Smyrna Beach, or perhaps a bit further south to New Smyrna proper. Either way, thanks to the century plus old Intracoastal Waterway, the Halifax is a northern extension of the Indian River Lagoon. Indeed, like its southern neighbor, the Halifax River is really an estuarine lagoon, heavily influenced by changing tides at Ponce Inlet as well as its more inland freshwater tributaries and canals.

As it happens, the Halifax River region has a long history of human use and modification. Native Americans were present thousands of years ago up to contact with Europeans in the 1500s. England established the King's Road (or Old King's Road), from southeast Georgia down to New Smyrna, just prior to the American Revolution. Several significant plantations appeared near the region's waterways in the early nineteenth century, but most of these were destroyed during the war with the Seminoles in the 1830s—yet their ruins dot the Halifax watershed. By the later nineteenth century, railroads made their way to the region, and after World War II, additional roads for cars and trucks opened the floodgates to development in the area. Much of the Halifax River is now lined with intensive development, which will soon be threatened by sea level rise.

The collection of papers in this edition of the *Florida Geographer* expands upon all these themes, and thanks to electronic publication, there are a host of informative maps and attractive photographs to illustrate ideas in the text. After guest editors Hyun Jung Cho and Michael Reiter set the stage for the papers that follow, Prof. Cho provides a photo essay on the Halifax River. Benjamin Tanner then combines several maps, spectacular photos, and insights from a range of reports to describe the region's alternating north/south ridges and their relationship to development patterns in the region. Charles Jacoby explains the network of waterways that feed the Halifax River as well as their historic use and occasional abuse over time. Kimberly Reiter outlines the historic development of mostly land transportation throughout the watershed—including the use of Daytona's beaches for auto transport and racing. Zach Zacharias uses several images from Hyun Jung Cho to briefly tell the story of the region's several early nineteenth century plantations. Janardan Mainali and Christopher de Bodisco use GIS and perspectives from economics to highlight the threat of projected sea level rise to intensive development along and near the Halifax River—and how we might handle rising seas moving forward. Michael Humphreys uses a restorative justice lens to ask if we might make better use of traditional ecological knowledge as a way of saving ourselves and honoring the long-departed Timucua Indians, who were ravaged mostly by European diseases for which they had no immunity. Finally, Michael Reiter does not just bemoan the loss of so much natural landscape in the region; he makes a plea for preserving more sensitive lands, partly for conservation biology reasons but also as a way of minimizing the damage from expected sea level rise.

I owe a giant debt of gratitude to Hyun Jung Cho and Michael Reiter of Bethune-Cookman University for their vision and work on this issue; and to each author who stayed the course, tolerated critiques with grace, and produced enlightening and thought-provoking essays. This special issue does not have any other review articles, book reviews, or my favorite Florida place essays. These features will resume in the next issue. As always, if you have research or an idea for an essay that might fit in this journal, please let me know. I am not hard to find: cmeindl@usf.edu

Warm Regards,

Christopher F. Meindl, Editor

The trails, roads, paths, and waterways of the Halifax River Urban Watershed: Drivers and reflections of a changing landscape

Hyun Jung Cho and Michael Reiter
Bethune-Cookman University

Globally, coastal urban areas are faced with numerous challenges that impact environmental and community resilience, including saltwater intrusion into aquifers and drinking water sources, flooding, and pollutant contamination of major waterways. These and other similar threats are expected to continue and worsen due to expanding urban development combined with the impacts of sea level rise. One such potentially impacted coastal area is the Halifax River (Figure 1), a 37-km long estuarine lagoon that runs along the eastern coast of Volusia County, Florida, with the city of Daytona Beach located centrally along its banks. The municipalities along the Halifax River include the coastal cities of Ormond Beach, Holly Hill, Daytona Beach, South Daytona, Port Orange, New Smyrna Beach, Daytona Shores, and Ponce Inlet.

Sustainability in its broad sense (ecological, social, economic, and technological) has been successfully used as a central place-branding theme in a number of cities and regions throughout the world. Coastal urban centers such as Daytona Beach could potentially benefit from preemptive repositioning and rebranding that adapts local assets to local and global environmental trends in order to promote sustainability/resilience while enhancing local economic activity and green tourism.

In January 2019, Bethune-Cookman University (B-CU), Stetson University, and other regional partners initiated the Halifax River Urban Watershed Sustainability Initiative (HRUWSI) to better understand and incorporate human dimensions and social factors into environmental research with the goal of assisting in the development of a sustainable, resilient coastal community capable of adaptation to changing coastal conditions. Thus far, the team produced a 23-minute documentary in summer 2019 that involved interviews of HRUW stakeholders, and a book titled *The Halifax River Urban Watershed: A Holistic Approach to Sustainability* (Cho et al. 2020).

Figure 1. The Halifax River is indicated in an open red oval.

That first publication on the HRUW described the area’s physical setting; history, human development, and culture; health and wellness profile; economic determinants; and considerations for restorative justice in the area. Our goal was to provide a broad foundational blueprint for a holistic

systems approach to the area's sustainability. This special issue of *The Florida Geographer* is the second collective publication on the HRUW by authors with diverse academic backgrounds.

The Florida Geographer appealed to us as an ideal portal for our next publications on the HRUW. Editor-in-Chief Christopher Meindl received our proposal with a positive attitude, acknowledging the relatively little public and governmental attention that the Halifax River receives compared to the St. Johns River, the Indian River Lagoon system, Lakes Apopka and Okeechobee, the Everglades, and Tampa and Apalachicola Bays. Our proposal was to examine different drivers for, and resultants of, landscapes (i.e. the eco-physical; the historical, cultural, and spiritual; the political and military; the economic and technological; etc.) and the respective interactions between humanity and landscape drivers within the HRUW.

The boundary of the HRUW is influenced by physical, social, historical, cultural, economic, and jurisdictional factors, so the actual geographic ranges covered in individual papers in this issue vary. But the primary geographic region of attention is the Halifax River watershed plus the adjoining area within and along the St. Johns River-to-Sea Loop (Figure 2). Indeed, it is often very difficult to describe developments in the HRUW without reference to activities in the surrounding land, rivers, and ocean.

An area's present perceptible landscape characteristics are the products of superimposed climate, underlying geology, natural surface features, past and current land use, and the builtscape, among which interactions overlap in time and space. Since the concept of landscapes is wide-ranging, our focus is on landscapes and drivers related to the formation and uses of rivers and water bodies, paths and trails, and roads and railroads in the HRUW. The interaction of different landscapes and likely drivers of change can be deduced from looking at a selected area and/or time through a variety of landscape lenses. Our proposal for this special issue was to explore the HRUW's trails, roads, paths, and waterways through various landscape lenses and to superimpose the views temporally and spatially.

Figure 2. The St Johns River-to-Sea Loop Multiuse Paved Trail

(Source: <https://river2sealooop.org/the-loop/>).

The different colors of the lines of the loop indicate the different stages of development following the Florida Department of Transportation's standard multi-color coding: green for existing trails; yellow for programmed or funded for construction; red for funded for pre-construction phases; and brown for not yet built.

Our goal is to better understand life connected to these features in the region's past as well as to identify and assess the current direction of the region's drivers of change and their impacts on present landscapes, from which we can forecast both likely future endpoints and alternative endpoints that might be more sustainable. Once the desired future endpoints are determined, we can assess the feasibility of that future and the policy measures required today to help reach that future.

That is how it began; and here we present to you the collection of articles on the HRUW from its geologic foundation, key waterways, historic transportation systems, historical conflicts and their ruins, urban growth, and the possibility of restorative justice regarding traditional environmental knowledge.

Acknowledgements: This second publication of the Halifax River Urban Watershed Sustainability Project would not have been possible without the assistance of several individuals and organizations. First, the Guest Editors for this special issue wish to thank *The Florida Geographer* Editor Christopher Meindl and Production Editor Cindy Shaw for their guidance and effort in making this special issue possible, and to the thoughtful review comments on the articles provided by the assigned reviewers of *The Florida Geographer*. We also wish to thank the article authors and their institutions for their contribution toward the project; their names and affiliations can be found in their respective works. Drs. Kimberly Reiter (Stetson University) and Michael Humphreys (Bethune-Cookman University) contributed comments and suggestions for several of the articles in this edition, and Emma Hastie, Lakean McGregor, and Jiyahna Price assisted with editing and formatting the final drafts of each article (Jiyahna and Lakean are supported by the NOAA-Center for Coastal and Marine Ecosystems II). We also thank Albert Hill, former Volusia County GIS Manager and President of Board Members of Central Florida GIS Workshop; he provided GIS data and shared his in-depth knowledge in Volusia County geography. This publication was made possible in part by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, Office of Education, Educational Partnership Program with Minority Serving Institutions award (NA21SEC4810004). Its contents are solely the responsibility of the award recipient and do not necessarily represent the official views of the U.S. Department of Commerce or National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration. Any opinions, findings, conclusions, or recommendations expressed in this publication are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the view of the U.S. Department of Commerce, National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration.

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Cho, H., M.A. Reiter, and C. Jacoby (eds.). 2020. *The Halifax River Urban Watershed: A Holistic Approach to Sustainability*. Daytona Beach: Bethune-Cookman University Press. 134 pp.

PHOTO ESSAY:

People and Landscape in the Halifax River Urban Watershed

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Figure 1. Sunrise on the Halifax River, Daytona Beach, Florida. Our proposal for this special issue was to explore the Halifax River Urban Watershed's trails, roads, paths, and waterways through various landscape lenses including both temporal and spatial dimensions. Photo taken on May 9, 2021 by Hyun Jung Cho.

Figure 2. Sunset on the Halifax River, Port Orange, Florida. Our intent is to better understand life connected to the landscape features in the region's past as well as to identify and assess the region's drivers of change and their impacts on present landscapes. Photo taken on June 7, 2013 by Hyun Jung Cho.

Figure 3. The golden hour at Halifax River, Port Orange, Florida. Humans often heavily manipulate the landscape. Photo taken on June 7, 2013 by Hyun Jung Cho.

Figure 4. People fishing at the pier under the Dunlawton Bridge. It is important to incorporate people into environmental research to assist in the development of a sustainable and resilient coastal community capable of adaptation to changing coastal conditions. Photo taken from the Dunlawton Bridge, Port Orange on May 9, 2021 by Hyun Jung Cho.

Figure 5. The remaining natural saltmarsh at a tidal creek where the Tomoka River joins the Halifax River. In its natural state, the area to the west of the Halifax River was a floodplain with wetland vegetation that drained slowly to the Tomoka River in the north or to Rose Bay in the south. Photo taken on April 5, 2020 by Hyun Jung Cho.

Figure 6. Natural marsh and mangrove shores along the southern Halifax River, Ponce Inlet, Florida. The Halifax River area lies within the narrow latitudinal zone of transition between herbaceous marshes and woody mangrove swamps. The tropical mangroves do not tolerate cold freezes; instead, salt marshes occur along the coasts within the temperate zone. With the reduced days of winter freezes, due to the changing climate, much of the marsh vegetation has been replaced by mangroves within the past decades in this transitional area. Photo taken on November 11, 2011 by Hyun Jung Cho.

Figure 7. Remaining dragline ditch in the Ormond Beach area. Saltmarsh mosquitos (*Aedes* sp.) lay their eggs in salt marshes. In order to remove the potential habitats for mosquito production, dragline ditches were dug in the 1950s and 1960s. The resultant ditches and spoils created the landscape that is either too deep or too high for the mosquitos to lay their eggs. Photo taken on April 5, 2020 by Hyun Jung Cho.

Figure 8. Oyster bed exposed during a low tide, Halifax River. Native Americans were drawn to the Halifax River area and its diverse array of food, especially the plentiful shellfish. Photo taken on November 23, 2011 by Hyun Jung Cho.

Figure 9. Facing west on the Main Street Bridge that crosses the Halifax River (a section of the Atlantic Intracoastal Waterway), Daytona Beach, Florida. The U.S. Army Corps of Engineers completed a series of canals between barrier islands and mainland along the east coast of Florida in 1912, with the Halifax River section representing one part of a 3,000-mile system that shelters boats as they travel along the Gulf of Mexico from south Texas to Apalachicola, Florida, and then up the Atlantic coast from Key West to Boston. This Intracoastal Waterway was completed in 1949 and is now federally maintained. Photo taken on March 29, 2020 by Hyun Jung Cho.

Figure 10. Main Street Bridge that crosses the Halifax River (a section of the Atlantic Intracoastal Waterway), Daytona Beach, Florida. Construction of the Intracoastal Waterway was not the only change affecting the Halifax River, as the existing 256,000-acre basin was altered significantly, modifying tidal exchange, floodplain drainage for agriculture and development, and construction of additional canals. Photo taken on March 29, 2020 by Hyun Jung Cho.

Figure 11. Broadway Bridge facing from the downtown Daytona Beach, Florida. The Broadway Bridge connects Daytona Beach downtown with the barrier island across the Halifax River. Photo taken on March 27, 2018 by Hyun Jung Cho.

Figure 12. Looking over the barrier island development from the Dunlawton Bridge, Port Orange, Florida. The Halifax is in the foreground and the Atlantic Ocean is behind the condominiums. The banks of the Halifax River are already heavily developed, and new developments are spreading across more inland areas. Photo taken on October 8, 2020 by Hyun Jung Cho.

Figure 13. Nova Canal (seen on the right side of the photo) runs along Nova Road (the northbound of the road is seen on the left side of the photo). Nova canal drains the untreated urban stormwater and channels it to the Halifax River through three outfalls. Permits for stormwater discharges or other activities regulated by the Florida Department of Environmental Protection or the St. Johns River Water Management District are particularly strict if they affect the Tomoka River and Spruce Creek because these waterbodies are designated as Outstanding Florida Waters. Photo taken on March 29, 2015 by Hyun Jung Cho.

Figure 14. The native submerged aquatic plant, American eelgrass (*Vallisneria americana*) growing lusciously in Reed Canal, one of the three stormwater outlets to the Halifax River, South Daytona, Florida. A series of similar canals delivers water to the Halifax River. Photo taken on March 29, 2015 by Hyun Jung Cho.

Figure 15. A mother duck and her ducklings in Nova Canal, Daytona Beach, Florida. With proper management, the stormwater system provides important urban ecosystem services and habitats for fish and wildlife. Photo taken on March 29, 2015 by Hyun Jung Cho.

Figure 16. Ormond Scenic Loop and Trail (shown here is the section of Old Dixie Highway between Bulow Creek State Park and Tomoka State Park), Ormond Beach, Florida. The King's Road remained the only viable land route south from St. Augustine until 1914. It was resurrected as State Route 4 in 1926. The surviving sections of the old State Route 4 have been found in the Plantation Oaks development along the Ormond Scenic Loop and Trail. Photo taken on April 5, 2020 by Hyun Jung Cho.

Figure 17. Forest along the Pershing Highway Interpretive Trail. Florida. Pershing Highway was built in 1917 to connect Daytona and Deland by paved road. After the highway was abandoned in 1947, it quickly fell to the forest. Photo taken on May 22, 2021 by Hyun Jung Cho.

Figure 18. Wild blackberries found along the Pershing Highway Interpretive Trail, Florida. The archaeological evidence of the region's early 1900s transportation network is hard to find. Even paved roads quickly disappeared into the Florida undergrowth if not maintained. Photo taken on May 22, 2021 by Hyun Jung Cho.

Figure 19. Blue Springs State Park, DeLand, Florida. Karst topography is common in the western portion of Volusia County. Sinkholes are abundant in the area and so are springs such as Volusia Blue, DeLeon, Gemini, and Green springs. Many Florida springs have long drawn tourists. Photo taken on August 21, 2021 by Hyun Jung Cho.

Figure 20. Early nineteenth century sugar mill ruins at Dunlawton, Port Orange, Florida. In the Battle of Dunlawton, Seminoles led by Coacoochee (Wildcat) greatly outnumbered and ambushed the local militia in early 1836. Photo taken on November 14, 2021 by Hyun Jung Cho.

Figure 21. Bulow Plantation Ruins Historic State Park. Major Benjamin Putnam and his militia, known as the "Mosquito Roarers," seized the largest and most profitable plantation, Bulowville. In January 1836, the militia ordered an evacuation of Bulow Station. After Putnam left, the Seminoles destroyed Bulowville, including the factory and the coquina main house. Today, Bulow Plantation Ruins Historic State Park provides visitors with a ghostly glimpse of the site's past. Photo taken on December 18, 2021 by Hyun Jung Cho.

Figure 22. The Old Fort Park Archeological Site, New Smyrna Beach, FL. The largest nineteenth century hotel in New Smyrna, owned by John Sheldon, was located on top of an ancient shell midden and old coquina ruins from the original 1765 Turnbull Colony. One can visit the coquina remains of the old Sheldon Hotel, which today is called the Old Fort Mound Park in Downtown Historic New Smyrna Beach. Photo taken on November 25, 2021 by Hyun Jung Cho.

Figure 23. The Casements, Ormond Beach, Florida. Built in 1913, The Casements was purchased by John D. Rockefeller in 1918 and was used as his winter mansion. It is now the Cultural Center for the City of Ormond Beach. Northern settlers were lured to the Halifax River area because of the promise of broad expanses, northern amenities and, above all, easy transportation access. Photo taken on April 5, 2020 by Hyun Jung Cho.

Figure 24. Motorcycles parked along Beach St. during the 2021 Daytona Beach Bike Week, Daytona Beach, Florida. Daytona Beach's annual Bike Week, a 10-day event held in March, is one of the events that draw people into this area. Photo taken on March 10, 2021 by Hyun Jung Cho.

Figure 25. Downtown Daytona Beach, Daytona Beach, Florida. The 3.8 percent population increase of Daytona Beach from 2020 to 2021 is significantly higher than both the US national trend and Florida trend (~0.1 % and 1.1%, respectively). Photo taken on May 9, 2021 by Hyun Jung Cho.

Figure 26. Eroded beach and collapsed seawalls after the 2022 Hurricanes Ian and Nicole. Increased hazard risks from sea level rise and more powerful hurricanes elevate insurance costs, making the cost of home ownership in Florida less affordable. Daytona Beach, Florida. Photo taken on November 28, 2022 by Hyun Jung Cho.

The Geologic Foundation of Halifax River Urban Watershed Waterways, Trails, Roads, and Canals

Benjamin Tanner, Stetson University

ABSTRACT

A series of Pliocene, Pleistocene, and Holocene ridges, and terraces, deposited as sea levels fluctuated during these times, built the geomorphic landscape that has interfaced with development patterns surrounding the Halifax River Urban Watershed in Volusia County, Florida. These ridges and terraces, which provide topographic relief and elevation on which to build, roughly parallel the modern shoreline given the underlying control of sea level and the resulting changes in the position of the ocean that formed these features. Karst topography is also present in the study area and represents another important geomorphic control on the landscape, especially in western Volusia County. Although the underlying geology of the region doesn't preclude development in lower lying areas given the ingenuity of humans, it does serve as an initial control on the location of towns, roads, and certainly waterways.

Keywords: Halifax River, Geology, Geomorphology, Development, Volusia County

INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this article is to provide the geologic and geomorphic context for the other contributions in this special issue on the Halifax River Urban Watershed and surrounding areas, especially as it relates to the history of development in the region. This article is confined geographically to Volusia County, Florida, and is not meant to be an exhaustive summary of the region's geology. This is also not the first summary of Volusia County's geology; other excellent summaries are available (German, 2009; Green et al., 2013b) and are used as part of the source material for the current contribution. This is a summary for the scholarly non-specialist, and, unlike past summaries, particular attention is paid herein to those aspects of the region's geomorphology that greatly influenced the area's development, in particular waterways, trails, roads, and canals.

UNDERLYING ROCKS

The geologic history most relevant to this special issue begins with the deposition of carbonates in Cenozoic times that are important in the building of the Florida Platform, namely the Eocene Avon Park Formation, the (later) Eocene Ocala Limestone, and the Miocene to Pliocene Hawthorn Group (Figure 1). A partial geologic time scale is provided to put the different ages discussed in this text into the context of relative and absolute time (Figure 2). General geologic histories of Florida feature these units prominently, and excellent summaries of that history are available (Scott, 1992a; Bryan et al., 2008; Hine, 2013). The Avon Park Formation and the Ocala Limestone were each deposited in a shallow marine environment that lacked siliciclastic sediments, and which was separated by water from the mass of the (now) North American Continent by the Gulf Trough (Bryan et al., 2008). The Hawthorn Group contains siliciclastic materials that provide evidence for the final connection, at that later time, of the Florida peninsula to the North American continent from which they were derived. That group also contains somewhat less abundant carbonates. The Avon Park Formation and Ocala Limestone contain carbonate rocks in high proportions, including limestone (especially the Ocala Limestone) and dolostone (especially the Avon Park Formation). These units provide the foundation on which subsequent sediments were deposited.

Figure 1. This cross section set from the geologic map of the study area illustrates how the Avon Park Formation and the Ocala Limestone occur at depth beneath a veneer of later unconsolidated sediment deposits. Cross section (A) lies in the northern part of Volusia County and runs from Lake George (left side of cross section) to the modern Atlantic Beach Ridge east of the Halifax River (right side of cross section). Cross section (B) runs from the southern edge of Lake Woodruff (left side of cross section) to near Spruce Creek (right side of cross section). Both cross sections are lightly modified from Green et al. (2013a).

Eon	Era	System, Subsystem/ Period, Subperiod	Series/ Epoch	Age estimates of boundaries in millions of years ago, or "mega- annum," unless otherwise noted	
	Cenozoic (Cz)	Quaternary (Q)	Holocene	11,700 ±99 yr ^m	
			Pleistocene		
		Tertiary (T)	Neogene (N)	Pliocene	2.588
				Miocene	5.332 ±0.005
			Paleogene (P)	Oligocene	23.03 ±0.05
					33.9 ±0.1
				Eocene	55.8 ±0.2
				Paleocene	65.5 ±0.3

Figure 2. Geologic time scale including relative and absolute ages of the Cenozoic Era, representing the most recent 65.5 million years of 4.6 billion years of Earth history. Modified from U.S. Geological Survey Geologic Names Committee (2010).

The Avon Park Formation, Ocala Limestone, and the Hawthorn Group are important in the study area because, in addition to providing a bedrock foundation for subsequent deposition, the carbonates contained within the units are susceptible to dissolution by acidic water. Rainwater is naturally acidic due to the reaction in the atmosphere of CO₂ (a relatively abundant gas) with H₂O to produce H₂CO₃ (carbonic acid). The typical pH of rainwater in this region is below 5 (Keresztesi et al., 2020). This low pH water moving through the soil and interacting with the carbonates picks up additional CO₂ from microbial activity. The subsequent interaction of these acids with carbonates that comprise the Florida Platform results in their partial dissolution and the formation of karst geomorphic features typical of Florida (and western Volusia County), including sinkholes and springs. The Avon Park Formation and Ocala Limestone are important for the storage and movement of groundwater associated with the Floridan Aquifer, which emerges through the

Hawthorn Group in places like DeLeon Spring. As we will see, these karst features are important to the development patterns of the region, especially how those patterns interface with tourism and recreation.

TERRACES AND RIDGES

Unconsolidated sediments, which were deposited as sea levels fluctuated through the Pliocene and especially Pleistocene, lie above the Avon Park, Ocala, and Hawthorn units (although not all are present in every area of the county). These sediments comprise terraces and ridges in the region as well, although many thousands of years of weathering, erosion, and transport have obscured much of the region's geologic story. A number of relatively flat terraces and intervening ridges and scarps are observed in eastern Florida, and these extend beyond the borders of Florida into other eastern U.S. states (Winker and Howard, 1977), although they are not continuous and their correlation with each other is often tenuous. These have been used to map relict shorelines and are described by Winker and Howard (1977, p.123) as having a topographic expression of “(1) linear or arcuate scarps facing seaward, (2) beach and dune ridges, and (3) ridge-and-swale lineations . . .” These features represent relict Pliocene and Pleistocene seaward-facing scarps, beach ridge and dune sets, and back-barrier deposits. Thus, these terraces and ridges have several different potential origins and are perhaps better referred to as geomorphic “complexes” or “sequences” (Burdett et al., 2013). The ridge and terrace nomenclature is used herein due to the geographic connection of place names in the region with the underlying geology (e.g., “DeLand Ridge, Rima Ridge”) and the historical use of these terms. Subsequent deformation of these ridge and terrace features has differentially impacted their horizontal position in space relative to sea level (Winker and Howard, 1977; Opdyke et al., 1984).

The terraces and ridges represent broad, relatively horizontal-lying sediments that were largely deposited in back-barrier, barrier, nearshore, and offshore environments similar to what one would find in the present day when crossing the bridge over the Halifax River, traveling over the barrier island system (encountering dunes, beach ridges, etc.), and moving across the shallow waters seaward of the modern beach onto the continental shelf—a relatively flat surface that slopes gently and generally down to the east for miles to tens of miles. Moving from west to east across the county, the terraces (which can each contain multiple sets of ridges and other linear features) become progressively lower in elevation and generally younger (Figure 3), and include the Penholoway Terrace (mid-to-late Pleistocene), Talbot Terrace (late Pleistocene), Pamlico Terrace

(late Pleistocene), and Silver Bluff Terrace (Pleistocene-Holocene transition and Holocene) (Bryan et al., 2008). The Halifax River, which represents an Estuarine Lagoon Complex in a geomorphic setting similar to the Indian River Lagoon (and just north of it), lies at a low position just to the west of the modern Atlantic Beach Ridge on the eastern, lower edge of the Silver Bluff Terrace. The Halifax is underlain by undifferentiated Pleistocene and Holocene coastal deposits consisting of sands, silts, and clays containing variable organics (Scott, 1992b). The western, landward edges of these terraces sometimes include associated ridges representing, along with the associated terrace, some former higher relative position of sea level (White, 1970; Figure 3). Named ridges present in Volusia County include (from west to east) Crescent City Ridge, DeLand Ridge, Rima Ridge, Atlantic Coastal Ridge, and the modern Atlantic Beach Ridge. These ridges contain components of former (and current in the case of the modern Atlantic Beach Ridge) beach/barrier systems including, but not limited to, shore-facing, wave-cut escarpments, bars, berms, and dune fields. Some of the larger ridges, such as the DeLand Ridge, are complicated and also contain terraces of multiple ages. It's worth mentioning that there are many ridges and associated shore-parallel features that are not named in the county. Sea level changes are continuous, so it makes sense that a single sea level fall, for example, could result in deposits of multiple coastal geomorphic features during its regression. It should also be noted that the terraces and ridges in the county are generally shore-parallel. This is not a coincidence given that they are associated with former positions of the ocean. These ridges and terraces are an important factor in the locations of development, roads, and waterways in the region.

Figure 3. This map and cross section illustrate the terraces and ridges present in Volusia County along with their elevations. This figure is slightly modified from German (2009).

It is tempting to imagine the elevations at which these ridges and terraces occur as being related directly to the position of higher former sea levels. Pliocene times were generally warmer than the present and sea levels were generally higher, mainly due to the diminished presence of glaciers that melted into the ocean during that time. Sea levels were generally lower but fluctuated greatly during the subsequent Quaternary “Ice Age,” alternating between lower positions during longer glacial periods and higher positions during the shorter interglacial periods. Figure 4 represents a global “eustatic” sea level history covering these times. Eustatic sea level histories relate to changes

in the actual mass or volume of the oceans. There are many reasons that local sea levels can change that have nothing to do with changes in ocean water volume. For example, uplift associated with plate tectonics can result in local sea level fall due to land being forced upward even when the volume of ocean water is increasing. There were several times when global eustatic sea levels were higher than present (Figure 4), and the deposition of terraces and ridges in Florida was certainly shaped by higher sea levels (Burdette et al., 2009). However, the position of these ridges and terraces in Florida cannot be used to produce a eustatic sea level history curve. This is because the land surface in this region is being uplifted. Some of the reasons for this uplift are thought to include hydro-isostatic adjustment of the land surface from glacial/interglacial cycles (the land mass moves as water and ice are added and removed from it), flexure of the lithosphere for a variety of reasons, isostatic uplift from sediment unloading (eroding a mass of sediment from the land causes it to uplift), and especially carbonate dissolution (dissolving a mass of limestone to create karst features like sinkholes, caves, and caverns causes the land to uplift) (Cronin et al., 1981; Adams et al., 2010). Therefore, the ridges and terraces that we observe at relatively high elevations in the region do not necessarily represent a former position of actual eustatic sea levels at those elevations, but instead represent a somewhat higher sea level and considerable subsequent uplift.

Figure 4. Global eustatic sea level history from 5 million years ago to the present. The horizontal “0” red line represents current sea level. Data for the graph are from de Boer et al. (2014). While it would be nice to illustrate when the various ridges and terraces were deposited on the sea level curve, it is important to note that detailed geologic work is required to estimate the ages of specific terrace and ridge features for a given location. The terraces discussed in the text extend up the Atlantic seaboard for many hundreds of miles, though are not necessarily continuous. Associations in space and time are tenuous and the geologic story is quite complicated (Burdette et al., 2013; Markewich et al., 2021). Given that detailed chronologic work has not been attempted in the immediate study area, general ages of terraces and ridges are omitted.

GEOLOGIC FEATURES AND HUMANS

The presence of shore-parallel terraces and ridges had several effects on development patterns in the region. Wetlands are present when the water table is at or near the land surface, or where the land is covered by shallow water (Cowardin, 1979), and thus wetlands are sensitive indicators of topographic position relative to the water table. It is obvious from a wetlands map of the region that many wetland areas in the county parallel the modern shoreline given their NW to SE trend (Figure 5). The higher positions where wetlands are not present include features like relict

dunes, beach ridges, or other linear features, with wetland areas occurring in adjacent lower areas, or swales. Note that all of the towns in the county listed on the map occur on or in close proximity to named ridges, including Pierson (Crescent City Ridge), DeLeon Springs, DeLand, and Deltona (DeLand Ridge), and Ormond Beach, Daytona Beach, Port Orange, New Smyrna Beach, and Edgewater (Atlantic Coastal Ridge). Dense road networks associated with these towns have developed on or near the named ridges, and relatively fewer roads cut across and through the extensive wetland areas between the ridges (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Wetland map of Volusia County and the surrounding region lightly modified from the Wetlands Mapper, National Wetlands Inventory, U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service. Note the abundant shore-parallel wetland areas between the DeLand area and the Daytona Beach area. Development is much more limited in that region.

These trends can also be seen in satellite photographs of the region along U.S. Highway 92, which connects DeLand and Daytona Beach (Figure 6). Increased development can be seen in

DeLand (DeLand Ridge), the area around Volusia County Jail (Rima Ridge), the mainland area of Daytona Beach (Atlantic Coastal Ridge), and also east of the Halifax River on beachside (modern Atlantic Beach Ridge). Also, development is certainly influenced by the presence of the Halifax River and the Ocean, given that land adjacent to these water bodies and others represent desirable locations for housing and business development. Of course, the locations of the inland water bodies are also heavily influenced by ridge and terrace development. Development is not confined solely to ridges. Humans have been filling wetlands and low areas in Florida throughout much of its history. It is obvious, though, that development patterns in the region are influenced by ridges. Humans are good at manipulating the landscape and building roads, and development perpendicular to and away from ridges is also common. However, the general trend is apparent. It is easier to build on dry land than in wetlands.

Figure 6. Satellite photograph showing development's association with named ridges, including DeLand (DeLand Ridge), Volusia County Jail and surrounding area (Rima Ridge), and Daytona Beach (Atlantic Coastal Ridge on mainland side, modern Atlantic Beach Ridge on beachside).

Drainage in the region is also influenced by the surficial geology of ridges and terraces. The Halifax River occurs on the eastern edge of the Silver Bluff Terrace, and that terrace is bounded by the Atlantic Coastal Ridge and the modern Atlantic Beach Ridge. Both Spruce Creek and the Tomoka River show a trellis drainage pattern (similar in appearance to a garden trellis), where smaller tributaries feed larger main channels at high angles. East to west drainage is rare in the region because rivers and streams must cross higher ridges such as the Atlantic Coastal Ridge, which also happens to be associated with consolidated coquina from the Anastasia Formation (White, 1970). Both Spruce Creek and the Tomoka River violate this pattern, but even these rivers follow the trend of the ridges along portions of their length (Figure 3). Spruce Creek forms an oxbow where it meets the Atlantic Coastal Ridge (Figure 7). The St. Johns River also runs parallel to ridges along most of its 300+ miles, from its headwaters, which in places is less than 10 miles from the tidal waters of Indian River Lagoon, all the way to near Jacksonville, where it finally crosses geomorphic high points and empties into the Atlantic Ocean.

Figure 7. Satellite photograph showing where an oxbow developed where Spruce Creek meets the Atlantic Coastal Ridge. Note the trend of the river along the Atlantic Coastal Ridge in this area.

The Anastasia formation warrants a brief discussion. It underlies portions of the Atlantic Coastal Ridge and modern Atlantic Beach Ridge (White, 1970). This formation consists of interbedded quartz sands and limestone beds that are composed of mollusk-rich shell fragments cemented together with calcite, known commonly as “coquina” (Schmidt et al., 1979). This formation outcrops naturally from St. Augustine down to southern Palm Beach County, where it grades into the Miami Limestone. The consolidated portions of this formation have been used as a building material since early European times in Florida. For example, it was quarried and used to build the Castillo de San Marcos, an early Spanish fort in St. Augustine. It has been used in other buildings as well and, among other things, has been used extensively for road base (Schmidt et al., 1979).

Karst topography is common in the western portion of Volusia County. There, dissolution of carbonates from the Avon Park Formation, Ocala Limestone, and the Hawthorn Group beneath overlying Pliocene and Pleistocene unconsolidated sediments has resulted in sinkholes and springs (Green et al., 2013b). Sinkholes are abundant in the area and so are springs (such as Volusia Blue, DeLeon, Gemini, and Green springs), as is obvious from a satellite photograph of a portion of the region (Figure 8). Many Florida springs have long drawn tourists (Kilby, 2020), and that history is highlighted in displays at both DeLeon Springs State Park and Blue Spring State Park.

Figure 8. Satellite photograph showing the location of DeLeon Spring near the western edge of the DeLand Ridge as well as abundant sinkholes in the western portion of Volusia County. Many of the ponds and lakes visible in the image are sinkholes.

VISITING THE SITES

Wonderful examples of the features discussed in this article can be found at several accessible locations across the county (Figure 9). A beautiful example of a Florida spring is easily accessible at DeLeon Springs State Park. There, water from the Floridan Aquifer runs out through the Coosawhatchie Formation of the Hawthorn Group (Figure 10). The prominence of the DeLand Ridge as it departs from the lower elevations of the Talbot Terrace is visible along Highway 92 (Figure 11). One can view lower elevations and flat-lying portions of the Talbot Terrace with wetlands present at the Pershing Highway pull-off next to Highway 92 (Figure 12). Sands derived from an ancient dune and beach ridge system are visible along Rima Ridge in the trails and dirt roads near Bennett Field Campground in Tiger Bay State Forest (Figure 13). Coquina limestone from the Anastasia Formation is visible along Spruce Creek adjacent to the Oxbow in the river as it meets the Atlantic Coastal Ridge at Volusia County's Doris Leeper-Spruce Creek Preserve (this location is

viewable on the Overlook Trail at the end of Martins Dairy Road or accessible by canoe or kayak launched in the Preserve; Figures 14 and 15). That is also a wonderful location to view the Atlantic Coastal Ridge. The Anastasia Formation also outcrops at the end of the trail that leads to the western end of Spruce Creek Preserve located along Sleepy Hollow Road (Figure 16). One can walk across a natural example of the modern Atlantic Beach Ridge and dune system on the trails at Ponce Preserve Municipal Park (Figure 17).

Figure 9. Satellite image showing major roads in the region along with the viewing locations of the features discussed in the text including DeLeon Springs State Park (A), the transition from lower areas of the Talbot Terrace to the DeLand Ridge (B), the low-lying areas of the Talbot Terrace visible around Pershing Highway pull-off (C), Rima Ridge visible around Bennett Field Campground (D), the Atlantic Coastal Ridge and outcrops of Anastasia Formation Coquina visible along the Overlook Trail at the end of Martins Dairy Road in Doris Leeper Preserve (E), Anastasia Formation coquina visible at the western edge of the portion of Doris Leeper Preserve at Sleepy Hollow Rd. (F), and a hike across the modern Atlantic Beach Ridge and dune system at Ponce Preserve Municipal Park (G).

Figure 10. Crowds gather around the spring on a warm summer day at DeLeon Springs State Park.
Image by author.

Figure 11. The transition onto the beginning of the DeLand Ridge on U.S. Highway 92 from lower elevations on the Talbot Terrace. Note that the water table is close to the ground surface in the ditch along the edge of the road at the lower elevation. Image courtesy of Sophie Tanner.

Figure 12. A remaining section of the old Pershing Highway at the pull-off adjacent to U.S. Highway 92 in Tiger Bay State Forest. Wetlands present at lower elevations of the Talbot Terrace are visible in places along the edge of the trail. Note the Black Bear visible on the old highway in the distance. Image courtesy of Sophie Tanner.

Figure 13. Dirt road near Bennett Field Campground in Tiger Bay State Forest that runs along Rima Ridge. Abundant sand, some of which is derived from ancient dunes, is present along the ridge. Image courtesy of Sophie Tanner.

Figure 14. The Atlantic Coastal Ridge is visible along Spruce Creek adjacent to the Oxbow in the river. It's difficult for water to find a path across the ridge, especially given that much of the ridge is underlain by Anastasia Formation coquina. That coquina is visible along the edge of the ridge at the location in this image, and is accessible by kayak or canoe, or viewable from the foot trail using binoculars. Photo courtesy of Sophie Tanner.

Figure 15. Close up image of the coquina from the Anastasia Formation visible at outcrop in the location pictured in Figure 14. Image courtesy of Sophie Tanner.

Figure 16. Outcrop of coquina from the Anastasia Formation visible in Doris Leeper Preserve at the end of the trail that goes to the western end of the preserve adjacent to Sleepy Hollow Rd. Image courtesy of Sophie Tanner.

Figure 17. View from the covered look-off in Ponce Preserve Municipal Park across dunes and ridges associated with the modern barrier island system, all within a natural setting at this location. A boulder from the Anastasia Formation is present near the west side parking lot (visible in inset). Trails take you along a boardwalk through salt marsh and mangrove to the Halifax River, across a maritime forest, and out to the beach. Images courtesy of Mena Tanner.

CONCLUSION

The field sites described above serve to illustrate the thesis of this paper, namely that the underlying geology influences development patterns in and around the Halifax River Urban Watershed. Ridges and terraces, primarily deposited during Pliocene and Quaternary fluctuations of sea level, provide the topographic relief for subsequent construction, which tends to occur on higher elevations. These patterns roughly parallel the modern shoreline given the underlying control of sea level and the resulting changes in the position of the ocean that formed these features. These features also constrain the position of waterways, such as Spruce Creek, the Tomoka River, and the Halifax itself. Karst topography is also important in the region and karst features such as springs have served as a draw for tourist activity, especially in western Volusia County. Although the underlying geology of the region does not preclude development in lower lying areas given the ingenuity of humans, it does serve as an initial control on the location of towns, roads, and certainly waterways.

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Key Waterways in the Halifax River Basin

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ABSTRACT

The basin of the Halifax River was formed over millennia, and it has been altered by people's activities in ways that lead to a need for restoration and protection. The basin was sculpted by changing sea levels, and falling sea levels exposed the barrier island that separates today's river from the Atlantic Ocean. Although labeled a river, the waterbody actually is a long, shallow estuarine lagoon that became brackish when the ocean washed over the barrier island. People have lived along the estuary for thousands of years because it facilitated transportation and provided valuable natural resources. The first major alterations to the watershed began in the mid-1800s when canals were dredged to create a safe inland passage for steamships and other vessels. In the 1920s, canals to drain the floodplain accommodated the new development demanded by an increasing population. Such large-scale alterations led to unforeseen detrimental impacts. Major portions of the basin became and remain impaired by high levels of nutrients and phytoplankton, low concentrations of dissolved oxygen, and the presence of bacteria that may indicate contamination with sewage. Partnerships with local, state, and federal agencies are addressing these and other impairments. Overall, the waterways of the Halifax River basin require restoration and protection.

Keywords: estuary, human activities, transport, impairment, restoration

EARLY HISTORY OF THE BASIN

The basin of the Halifax River was sculpted by rising and falling sea levels, and today's watershed appeared thousands of years ago during a period when sea levels were generally falling (Figure 1; Bonnie Holub and Associates, 1998). Falling sea levels exposed offshore sandbars that had solidified into rock (lithified), and these formations became the barrier island that separates the Halifax River from the Atlantic Ocean (Bonnie Holub and Associates, 1998). Although labeled a river, the waterbody actually is a long, shallow estuarine lagoon that became brackish after the last time sea level rose and washed over the barrier island (Bonnie Holub and Associates, 1998). Along the western edge of the basin are terraces and ridges representing previous shorelines (MacNeil, 1949). In its natural state, the area to the west of the Halifax River was a floodplain with wetland vegetation that drained slowly to the Tomoka River in the north or to Rose Bay in the south because the ridges prevented the water from flowing to the Halifax River (MacNeil, 1949; Bonnie Holub and Associates, 1998). Rainfall on the barrier island drained to the river or the Atlantic Ocean (Bonnie Holub and Associates, 1998).

Figure 1. Geomorphology around the Halifax River, including associated marine terraces and ridges (adapted from Knochenmus and Beard, 1971).

Native Americans were drawn to the estuary and its diverse array of food, especially the plentiful shellfish (Bonnie Holub and Associates, 1998). In fact, the most pronounced evidence of these early settlements are middens or hills comprised of discarded shells. The Timucua established villages, such as Nocoroco on Tomoka Point where the Tomoka River joins the Halifax River (Figure 2). As their numbers grew, the people in these settlements developed social and political structures that helped maintain order. The early inhabitants of these settlements relied on the river as a connection that supported trade routes. The Timucua were all but wiped out by 1763 due to their lack of immunity to diseases like measles that came with European settlers.

Figure 2. Nocoroco as described by Alvaro Mexia (<https://www.floridastateparks.org/learn/native-american-and-plantation-history>).

From 1500 to 1800, European settlers established settlements and plantations along the Halifax River (Bonnie Holub and Associates, 1998). New crops were introduced to the region and timber was exported, with the river continuing to act as a food source and trade route (Figure 3). The Spanish traded Florida to Britain in exchange for Cuba in 1763, and the British government gave land grants to those willing to move to the new territory. Spain regained control of Florida through the Treaty of Paris signed in 1783, but many Britons remained, and few Spaniards

immigrated to the reclaimed territory. In 1819, after the First Seminole War, eastern Florida was ceded to the United States and, ultimately, the United States acquired all of what is now Florida.

Figure 3. A plantation growing rice near the Tomoka River

(<https://www.floridastateparks.org/learn/native-american-and-plantation-history>).

MAJOR CHANGES TO THE BASIN

In 1855, the Florida General Assembly passed the Internal Improvement Act, which was designed to encourage construction of canals and railroads and promote growth (Bonnie Holub and Associates, 1998; Haydt and Frazel Inc., 2003). In 1874, an amendment to this act made it possible to grant free land along newly constructed canals and railroads. This approach was applied in 1881–1883 when the Florida Coast Line Canal and Transportation Company received a charter to cut canals linking the Matanzas and Halifax rivers, which included 35 miles of canals that ultimately allowed small vessels such as steamboats to travel the 234 miles from St. Augustine to Jupiter more safely. The company was granted adjacent land for each mile of the canal they dug, with the total grant being 1,030,128 acres. The series of canals along the east coast of Florida was completed in 1912, with the Halifax River section representing one part of a 3,000-mile system that shelters boats

as they travel along the Gulf of Mexico from south Texas to Apalachicola, Florida, and then up the Atlantic coast from Key West to Boston (Figure 4). This Intracoastal Waterway was completed in 1949 and is now federally maintained.

Figure 4. National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration chart showing part of the federally maintained Intracoastal Waterway as parallel dashed lines.

Construction of the Intracoastal Waterway was not the only change affecting the Halifax River, as the existing 256,000-acre basin was altered significantly (Haydt and Frazel Inc. 2003). Tidal exchange was modified because the Intracoastal Waterway allowed some exchange from Matanzas Inlet in the north, which augmented exchange coming through Ponce de Leon Inlet at the southern end of the river. Efforts to drain the floodplain for agriculture and development began in the 1920s with the formation of the Halifax Drainage District. The original goal was to drain a long, narrow area covering 10.4 square miles at an estimated cost of \$160,000. To accommodate development, canals were added or enlarged to carry more water. Now, a series of canals delivers water to the Halifax River along with the natural waterways and tributaries that comprise Bulow Creek, the Tomoka River, and Spruce Creek (Figure 5). The system of canals has three main points of discharge, with the 11th Street Canal and the Reed Canal discharging to the Halifax River and the Halifax Canal discharging to Rose Bay.

Figure 5. Open canals (dark blue lines) in and adjacent to the Halifax River Basin (red outline). Map of canals courtesy of the Volusia County Road and Bridge Department.

UNFORSEEN CONSEQUENCES AND SUBSEQUENT RESPONSES

The canals bring more water, nutrients, and sediments to the Halifax River and its tributaries faster than they would have been delivered naturally (Magley, 2013a, b, c, d). In combination with more intensive land use in the basin, this altered hydrology has led to impairment (Figure 6). Major portions of the Halifax River, Spruce Creek, and the Tomoka River do not meet the relevant standards for water quality due to high levels of chlorophyll-*a* (a pigment that plays a role in photosynthesis in algae and plants and, in this case, is indicative of elevated quantities of algae); elevated levels of nitrogen and phosphorus (nutrients that all living things need, but which in high quantities exacerbate levels of chlorophyll-*a* by stimulating the growth of single-celled algae called phytoplankton); low levels of dissolved oxygen (a condition that stresses fish and other aquatic animals); or the presence of undesirable levels of fecal coliforms (bacteria that may indicate contamination with sewage or animal waste).

Figure 6. Documents outlining total maximum daily loads (TMDLs) for impaired waters in the Halifax River Basin.

Impairments are being addressed by Volusia County, local municipalities, and other relevant parties (Adair, 2021). Such efforts include upgrades to wastewater treatment plants, improved treatment of stormwater, water conservation, planning and regulation to prevent increases in loads of nutrients from new development, acquisition of land that protects groundwater and controls floods, collection of data to track progress and identify problems, and education to encourage sustainable behavior (Figure 7). Permits for stormwater discharges or other activities regulated by the Florida Department of Environmental Protection or the St. Johns River Water Management

District are particularly strict if they affect the Tomoka River and Spruce Creek because these waterbodies are designated as Outstanding Florida Waters.

What the county is doing:

19	Planning and regulation	Projects	Acquisition	Data collection and education
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> □ County-wide Environmental Minimum Standards □ Comprehensive Plan policies □ Land Development Code regulations (applies to the 73% of un-incorporated county) □ Implementing state rules 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> □ Water Quality Plan □ Mosquito Lagoon reasonable Assurance Plan □ Stormwater Improvement projects □ Wastewater treatment plant upgrades and expansions □ Water Conservation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> □ Approximately 40,000 acres of conservation land that protects wetlands and aquifer recharge areas, and provides flood control 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> □ Surface water quality monitoring □ Save our Spring and Rivers campaign □ Green Volusia □ Education programs

Figure 7. Volusia County’s efforts to address impaired waters (adapted from Adair, 2021).

Other major alterations affecting waterways in the Halifax River basin are causeways that reduce the circulation of water. Rose Bay epitomizes this issue (U.S. Army Corps of Engineers, 2002). Rose Bay is a brackish waterbody to the south of Port Orange connected to the Halifax River via Spruce Creek and has water depths of three feet or less in most places. An abandoned earthen causeway built to carry a road across the bay, and another causeway bearing an active road, were built near the connection to Spruce Creek. The reduced circulation created by the causeways along with intense urbanization degraded water quality in Rose Bay. Circulation improved after authorities removed the abandoned causeway and replaced the active causeway with a bridge, and internal loads of nutrients decreased after 280,000 cubic yards of sediment were removed (Figure 8). In combination with improved treatment of stormwater and replacing septic systems with connections to sewage treatment plants, these changes led to improvements in Rose Bay’s water quality and habitats—a successful restoration.

Figure 8. Plan for the restoration of Rose Bay (adapted from the United States Army Corps of Engineers, 2002). ① = control stormwater pollution; ② eliminate discharges from septic tanks; ③ = remove a causeway when replacing the bridge for US Highway 1; ④ = remove the abandoned causeway; ⑤ = remove accumulated sediment.

Surface waters in the Halifax River basin have been altered and the resulting unforeseen detrimental changes are being addressed. In addition, surface water is linked inextricably to groundwater because of the region's karst topography (Knochenmus and Beard, 1971). Within the basin, there are areas of moderate and high groundwater recharge; that is, areas where substantial amounts of rainfall can rapidly infiltrate and enter the underlying aquifers (Figure 9; McKenzie-Arenberg, 1989). Canals that drain wetlands west of the Halifax River remove water from the landscape rapidly and reduce the rate of recharge, which can lead to saltwater intrusion into groundwater and reduced discharge from springs (McKenzie-Arenberg, 1989). Less groundwater recharge and more saltwater intrusion can increase the cost of treating drinking water because groundwater represents the primary source of drinking water in the region. Reduced groundwater discharge also affects the ecology and aesthetics of nearby springs, with increased growth of

nuisance algae being one consequence of concern. In both cases, there can be serious economic consequences if development or tourism is hampered.

These problems have led to regional aquifer management plans and other plans that propose a variety of techniques to reduce consumption and enhance recharge (Marshall, Provost and Associates, 1995; PBS&J, 2002; Quentin L. Hampton Associates, Inc. and PBS&J, 2002). For example, Tiger Bay is drained by Tiger Bay Canal into a channel that leads to the Bennett Swamp, and from there into the Tomoka River via Thayer Canal, among others. Problems arose when the demand for water from a growing population altered groundwater levels and flows to natural wetlands. One solution, completed in 2016, was to build a weir that both spreads water across the wetland so that it can recharge the aquifer and returns flows to the Halifax River to a more natural state (Freeman, 2003).

Figure 9. Regions of groundwater recharge (adapted from McKenzie-Arenberg, 1989).

CONCLUSION

In summary, the Halifax River represents a major feature of the east-central coast of Florida. It influenced the lives of people for thousands of years, and in recent centuries people have exerted considerable influence on the river and its watershed. Some of these actions have led to undesirable consequences, and those consequences are being addressed. The sustainability of the Halifax River, its ecology, and the people it supports depends on the successful restoration and protection of its natural conditions (Figure 10; Cho and Reiter, 2020).

Figure 10. Spruce Creek in its natural state in an undated photo, courtesy of the digital archives of the Halifax Historical Society Museum, Daytona Beach, Florida.

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Wheels: Historic Transportation Systems and Landscape in the Halifax Watershed

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ABSTRACT

This paper explores the history of transportation systems in the Halifax River Watershed from an environmental perspective. Emphasis is placed on the negligible environmental impact of early roads as compared to the late nineteenth century and twentieth century railroads, paved roads, and permanent bridges. The early introduction of the automobile to the Halifax region, the appeal of the area as an affordable vacation destination, and the desire for an automobile-friendly transportation grid would have a permanent and destructive impact on the Halifax River watershed.

Keywords: Halifax River, roads, Daytona Beach, transportation

A note on some of the primary sources used in this paper:

Numbers in text next to the following sources refer to accession/file numbers of the cited documents.

HHS = Halifax Historical Society, Archives, Daytona Beach.

MOAS = Museum of Arts and Sciences, Cici and Hyatt Brown Museum of Art, Daytona Beach.

SLAF = State Library and Archives of Florida, Florida Photographic Collection, Tallahassee.

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INTRODUCTION: SOURCES AND EARLIEST RECORDS

A modern aerial view of the Halifax River Watershed reveals a thickly wooded landscape away from the river, but a dense and planned development network adjacent to the river. The modern environmental impacts of such a dense system are covered elsewhere in this special issue. This article is more concerned with the historical development of the extensive transport network and its initial impacts on the watershed.

The sources available for identifying that impact are uneven to say the least. A few academic monographs have been written on the greater metropolitan areas in North, South and West Florida (Ingram, 2014; Karnes, 2009; Gannon, 2003), but monographs specific to the Halifax area were written mostly by local agencies and historians. One broader work is Bruce Seely's *Building the American Highway System: Engineers as Policy Makers* (Seely, 1987). However, while focused on national highway building, Seely studies road building as an engineering problem, not an environmental challenge. This is in keeping with most of the scholarship on roads in the watershed. Any attention to the region's environment has in general been given to the physical challenges that the forested wetlands of the Halifax watershed presented, not to any immediate or long-term environmental impacts. There is a great deal of local research on the important agents and entrepreneurs such as Henry Flagler and Carl Fisher and their 'taming' of the hostile Florida environment, although the majority of it is written for a general public. For most local histories, such progressivist and person-centered histories are completely understandable, but are far less interested in environmental impact than on social development. Where environmental consequences are usually addressed, they are typically found in the more than plentiful and adequate regional scholarship on tourism brought by roads, rails, and airports. However, very little is specific to the Halifax region (Stager and Carver, 2006; Jakle and Sculle, 2005; Belasco, 1979). As the enthusiasm for extensive automobile roads evolved hand-in-hand with the history of flight in the Halifax region, and as both fed the tourism industry, reactions to environmental impacts of road and runway construction are not well addressed in the sources. Most pamphlets and travel guides of the period speak glowingly of the transportation network (e.g. DeLand, Florida, 1900).

The archaeological evidence is also challenging. Before the creation of the Dixie Highway, roads in Florida left little trace on the landscape. Even paved roads quickly disappeared into the Florida undergrowth if not maintained. A good example of this effect is the so-called Pershing Highway, built in 1917, to connect Daytona and DeLand by paved road. Early photographs show a cleared landscape along the road and careful brickwork. However, after the highway was abandoned

in 1947, it quickly fell to the forest. Despite less than eighty years of disuse, only a preserved 2.3-mile stretch, discovered after wildfires swept the area in the early twenty-first century, survives as an interpretive trail off U.S. Highway 92 near Highridge Estates (Williamson, 2008). It is easy to see why important historic roads without permanent surfaces, like the Old King's Road, leave almost no trace at all, or have been incorporated under contemporary paved roads.

In short, there is little discussion of the historic environmental repercussions of the transportation boom in the Halifax watershed between the late nineteenth and mid-twentieth century. There is also a lack of introspection on the impact that road building would have on the political, social, and cultural development of Volusia County in general.

This article will not deal with the environmental consequences that accompanied the development of the Halifax River as a transportation waterway. That is covered elsewhere (Reiter, 2020). Nonetheless, for a good portion of the watershed's human history, the river remained the primary mode of transportation (Reiter, 2020). The native Timucua moved by canoe through the rich oyster beds of the Halifax, and by trackway, as had their ancestors. Their shell middens tell a story of the Floridian diet as early as 7000 years ago (Saunders and Russo, 2011). While this is not the place to discuss the fauna of the middens in detail, there is growing evidence that middens served as directional markers in other parts of the Mesolithic world (Mellars, 2004). In Florida as elsewhere, the evidence suggests that they were not simply refuse heaps; they may have had ancestral significance besides marking the land. Some see importance in their placement in the landscape, but for this we would need a careful understanding of how the landscape looked when the midden was laid down, a difficult task as so many have been mined for their easy shell. In any case, there would seem to be more to them than dump sites (O'Donohue, 2017). Halifax middens are predominantly composed of oysters, with other bone and shell deposits. Whether or not the placement of Florida middens might reflect specific and complex markers rather than simple trash heaps, they remained obvious to travelers on the Halifax in the early twentieth century and would be used later in road construction (Johnson, 1918).

Trackways, generational routes that utilized high ground, lines of sight, and natural or constructed markers, are more complicated as they leave little to no archaeological trace, although we can use evidence from other heavily forested areas to hypothesize logical paths (Darvill, 2002). Beyond the coastline, native Floridians lived in an environment of limited horizons. There were clearings but very little open ground. In other words, the Halifax watershed may have been riddled with trackways, but their purpose was as short connectors in a world of small horizons beyond the

riverbanks. The Halifax and St. John Rivers were the most practical conduits, and it is no coincidence that settlement favored those shores.

Historically, Volusia County's transportation grid reflects the difficulties of travel beyond the river before the arrival of the railroad (Reiter, 2020). However, even the introduction of rail travel did little to develop the Halifax area beyond Daytona Beach for two reasons. First, a good deal of the rail traffic was commercial, and followed the easy path of the rivers to connect southern Florida with Jacksonville. Second, passenger traffic catered to the better heeled at first, most of whom were travelling to coastal resorts (Reiter, 2020). Anyone wishing to be west of that area would take steamers down the St. Johns to DeLand and Orange City. Even the invention of the automobile at first impacted only the urbanized coastline of the Halifax. While other areas of the country could be accessed by horse, the thick Florida forests proved an extra challenge for roadbuilding.

The honor of the first recorded road in the Halifax watershed belongs to the mid-eighteenth-century Old King's Road, commissioned under Governor John Grant of the British East India Company in 1763 and connecting St. Augustine to Andrew Turnbull's settlement at New Smyrna by 1776 (Ryan, 2012; Schene, 1976). The coquina- and crushed oyster-topped road allowed development of sugar, indigo, and rice plantations along its route. The plan was a failure for Grant, as the region never developed the settlements and smaller plantations that would contribute to a thriving chain of communities. Most maintained roads were private and managed by large plantations in the area such as the Bulow Plantation (Reiter, 2020). The Old King's Road was effectively for haulage of sugar, indigo, and rice, and was a broad, tamped down sand road with little environmental impact. Much of our understanding of its route and purpose are determined not by the road but by the plantation ruins on either side, and the evidence for extensive modification of the land for high impact crops.

Despite the fact that it was one of only two well developed trackways in the entire Florida territory (the Spanish Trail between St. Augustine and Pensacola being the other), the King's Road was effectively abandoned after 1783 when the Spanish took control of Florida and several of the Halifax plantations were abandoned (Liston, 1996; WPA, 1939). Improvements came after 1827 and the United States' control of the region. While the local residents had petitioned for improvement, the army needed a reliable conduit into Seminole territory as well.

Despite its disuse after the Seminole Wars and the failure to build a connecting bridge across the Tomoka River, the King's Road remained the only viable land route south from St. Augustine until 1914. The road appears on 1837 and 1851 maps and may have been palm tree lined by then

(Liston, 1996) but, because the road was never supplied with the crucial bridge, it became little more than a woodland trail after the Civil War. While it was resurrected as State Route 4 in 1926, the route now followed the railroad. What environmental impact it may have had in its construction and in the early adjacent plantation houses was effectively erased by Florida's vegetation. Surviving sections have been found in the Plantation Oaks development along the Ormond Scenic Loop and Trail (Moore, 2021; Schene, 1976), and some pilings and causeway of indeterminate date remain in the Pellicer Creek area. For its day, however, the King's Road was a remarkable piece of wetland engineering (Ryan, 2012). When sections were rediscovered in the 1880s, the abandoned road was still high and level in places.

The King's Road could not guarantee safety after the Seminole Wars in the 1830s, and the Halifax region was effectively abandoned until after the Civil War except for lumbering and turpentine camps. As it was easier to ship these products by river to Mosquito Inlet, the King's Road fell into overgrown decay. The only roads in use were tracks for the lumbermen and the scattered seasonal camps, which were quickly reclaimed by the regional vegetation. The St. Johns River region to the west, on the other hand, benefitted from its easy steamer connections to Jacksonville, but at the time of incorporation as Volusia County in 1854, there remained only thirty-eight families registered in the entire county (Liston, 1996). Roads were of little concern for those near rivers, and the area was considered useless for anything beyond slave-driven plantation use. Only five families lived in the eastern side, two of them on the Halifax (Liston, 1996). Mail moved from Enterprise to New Smyrna for distribution (Schene, 1976). The river and local forests were impacted by lumbering and turpentine gouging of trees, but lumber roads were rough and easily reclaimed after use.

Although settlement increased after the Civil War, there remained no immediate need for roadbuilding. Liston (1996) recounts the story of early settler Andrew Bostrom, an orange grower and founder of Ormond Beach who served on the Volusia County Board of Commissioners in the late 1860s. To attend a board meeting, Bostrom would sail to Port Orange and walk the thirty miles to the county seat at Enterprise in a wet two-day trek (Figure 1). If one did not want to brave the dangerous shoals of the Mosquito Inlet, the walk from the Matanzas Inlet to the Halifax was twenty-seven miles through sloping sand (Reiter, 2020; Liston, 1996). For most of this period, the river remained the main artery of communication, and investment for improvements were directed towards river needs (Reiter, 2020).

Figure 1: Volusia County in 1860. Source: Samuel Augustus Mitchell. 1860. *Mitchell's New General Atlas*. Philadelphia: S.A. Mitchell. See: <http://fcit.usf.edu/florida/maps/pages/400/f418/f418.htm>

DAYTONA AND THE RAILROADS

The impetus for designing the first network of sustainable roads came with the founding of Daytona in the 1870s. The planners, originally led by Matthias Day of Ohio, envisioned broad streets lined with trees and large lots for houses. While one could not call Day an incipient environmentalist, his vision of trees, gardens, and open spaces for play informed his idea of how the streets should be designed (Liston, 1996). Those who succeeded Day when he had to drop out of the project carried the same idea of promoting the area as a southern paradise (MOAS, Coll 001617). By 1873, J. W. Smith advertised lots for the short-lived community of Memento (Schene, 1976), and Ormond was homesteaded in 1875. On Oceanside, the beach was used as the first reliable roadway, at least during low tide. A mid-sixteenth century account of the region by Ernst d'Erlach, a French Huguenot who survived the Spanish massacre of Fort Caroline in 1565 and by tradition married into the local Timucuan tribe in 1566, describes the beach in his journals as “. . . hard and broad enough to march a large army over it in ranked battalions . . .” (as quoted in Liston, 1996, p.16).

In 1876, a new stage road connected Daytona to Volusia Landing on the St. Johns River. The King's Road again saw improvements for a regular three-day stagecoach run to Jacksonville, helped by a daily ferry service across the Tomoka River first recorded in 1881. By 1884 the community of Seabreeze was advertised on plat maps as a health resort provided with modern streets and devoted to restoring the mind through natural surroundings: "A Home on the Halifax Peninsula means Health, Long Life and Contentment" (Weaver, 2011; HHS, 1998, 35) The original plats suggest lots sold quickly. Other developers followed, laying out street grids on both sides of the Halifax. The intentions first voiced by Day to maintain level streets lined with trees and fronted with extensive lawn continued, if only to attract northern settlers who were lured with the promise of broad expanses, northern amenities and, above all, easy transportation access.

By the 1890s, Daytona had been platted out as a growing town with many streets (HHS 1999, 117.1). Beach Street, a business-lined shell road along the river, was built up and surfaced by 1914 to accommodate the boom in tourist hotels. However, Daytona remained a very small town, servicing the well-off winter crowd and processing lumber and produce from the inland county for the intermittent freighters off Mosquito Lagoon that brought in regular supplies in exchange (WPA, 1939). Johnson (1918) notes that palmetto and live oak still dominated the landscape beyond the junction of the Tomoka River. The bridging of this river in 1887 allowed the St. Johns and Halifax River Railroad to reach Daytona. At that point the entire Halifax region lay open to the outside world and the permanent changes that such development entailed.

The story of Flagler's railroads and their environmental impact is discussed elsewhere (Reiter, 2020). In sum, there was initially little interest in railroad investment in the Halifax region because of the very low population compared to Jacksonville, Tampa, and Key West (Corliss, 1960). When Albert P. Sawyer obtained a large section of a land-grant to create an inland waterway on the east coast of Florida in 1881 via the Florida Coast Line Canal and Transportation Company (Akin, 1979), he asked Henry Flagler to help with dredging equipment. Flagler took over the company and combined it with his Jacksonville, St. Augustine, and Halifax River Railway (JSH) and his St. Johns and Halifax Railway to form the powerful Florida East Coast Railway in 1885 (Doherty, 1980; Akin, 1979). Flagler's impact in the Halifax River watershed began with the acquisition of a narrow-gauge lumber track that ran from East Palatka to Daytona. By 1887, Flagler's 'White Railroad' (named after the original owner James Utley White) connected the coastal towns and DeLand to St. Augustine by way of Palatka (Doherty, 1980). From this would come the nucleus of the Florida East Coast Railway (WPA, 1939). For Flagler, the Daytona terminus was a crucial acquisition, as it allowed him

to purchase and develop the island in the Halifax River today called City Island and utilize it for his river freight terminal (WPA 1939). Flagler also bought and rebuilt roads to Ormond and Daytona, purchasing and refurbishing the Hotel Ormond in 1892 and bridging the Halifax River (Corliss, 1960).

Unlike earlier roads, railways brought noticeable destruction to the Halifax region. Railroad construction in itself required extensive clear-cutting to allow manpower, supplies, camps, and building equipment access to the proposed route. The scarring was dramatic even before the first rail was set. To negotiate the large logs that had to be cleared along the path, railroad workers used carts fitted with heavy wheels six feet in diameter. Repeated trips wore down the sand tracks, creating rutted gullies that worsened in the rain and wetlands. Coal spillage was common along the rails as well. Coal and wood smoke killed trees on either side of the tracks, while the noise altered wildlife patterns. Erosion increased in the banked areas, requiring constant maintenance while choking the waterways.

Streams and wetlands were the most impacted, as fill was brought in to create sturdy weight-bearing platforms. When workers paved the St. Johns and Halifax River Railroad in 1885, they were stymied at the Tomoka River wetlands, and spent a year dumping dirt into the swamp before they resorted to a large, crisscrossed log road to retain the dirt. They then threw the construction engine into the swamp to dispose of it. The line was hailed as a blessing in Ormond when it arrived in November 1885 but left a scarred landscape and disturbed wetland system in its wake. In fact, the railroad was so shoddily made that Flagler later had the entire track replaced and rebuilt, adding to the scarring (Liston, 1996).

Another trend initiated by the railroads was hostelry. Settlements along the King's Road and Halifax River provided for travelers and coaches, but Flagler expressed dissatisfaction with amenities on Florida's east coast and invested in luxury hotels that built their reputations upon lush and exotic Floridian landscapes. Prior to this, hostleries appeared where there were people already in sufficient number to support a coach stop. Now the trend reversed, hotels serving as anchors for new communities that flourished with the rise in tourism.

In anticipation of the tourism benefits brought by the new railway system, wealthy residents and developers encouraged bridge construction across the Halifax to Ormond, Seabreeze, and Daytona Beach to replace the steam ferry service (Schene, 1976). In the mid-1880s, Ormond built a wooden drawbridge on the site of the current Granada Bridge capable of supporting carriage traffic and leading directly to the luxurious Hotel Ormond completed in 1888. Daytona followed with the

South Bridge to Silver Beach and North Bridge (Main Street). By 1902, a third bridge connected Mason Avenue to Seabreeze.

The impact of these bridges on the Halifax watershed was minimal. Many homes were built with brick, coquina, and some concrete, but the infrastructure of the developments, not to mention the bridges, required large amounts of local wood. While the growth of Daytona and bridge construction contributed to local deforestation, most of the lumber was taken through the already established industry that filtered through Daytona. However, in 1913 Daytona built its first concrete bridge to accommodate automobiles and trucking. While in use only twenty-five years, it would mark the beginning of permanent construction of the Mason, Oakridge, Halifax, Main Street, Speedway and Orange Avenue Bridges in the mid-twentieth century and would require reinforced banks, shoreline infrastructure, and central dredging. There was also increased runoff of various pollutants from the bridges. The ease of crossing the Halifax was a major factor in the great development boom that followed, but the construction of bridges marked one of the first permanent impacts on the Halifax River.

Key to much of this activity to construct permanent bridges was the introduction of automobiles to the Halifax region in 1901. The elites of Ormond and Daytona who introduced the expensive new toys in celebration of their status soon discovered that the tires could not grip the sandy soils of regional roads and pressed for smooth, hard chip roads for their vehicles (SLAF, 30712; MOAS, 001988). Beach Street, still a dirt road in 1910 (MOAS, 001639), was soon paved in brick. By 1914 the Daytona Fire Department boasted automotive trucks (HHS Photo Collection, Street Scenes Bk. 2). While the coquina paving, ‘marled’ crushed rock and pine needles inside Daytona and DeLand proved adequate, any journeys in between were hazardous and best done by slow horse and team.

In the western portion of the county, road development remained slow despite the rush of settlers to Enterprise, Volusia Landing, Orange City and DeLand (Figure 2). The St. Johns River was a reliable and rapid highway to Jacksonville, and roads in general remained as local or commercial trackways to the river (Liston, 1996). In 1900, it took twelve hours to make the 25-mile journey from Daytona to DeLand, although one automobile daredevil made it in two hours in 1903 (Hebel, 1955; Fitzgerald, 1937). A shell road would not connect the two communities until 1907.

Figure 2: Emerging road network in Volusia County, 1897. Source: *The Century Atlas of Florida*. 1897. New York: The Century Co.

Part of the issue was that, beyond Orange City and the county seat of DeLand, the western side of Volusia remained agricultural and conservative. Few automobiles travelled beyond DeLand streets until the 1920s. Cattlemen disliked the new automobiles and the tourists they brought. Branch roads remained narrow and soft, reflecting the low incidence of automobiles in the western portion of the county where gravel continued to be laid by horse drawn rollers (SLAF, 396). Horses remained a common sight on west Volusia roads. The most visited tourist destination on the west side of the county, DeLeon Springs, was accessible only by a narrow forest sand track into the 1920s (SLAF, 11634; 139711).

By 1902, the road connecting Ormond to Daytona was marled to accommodate the new automobiles, cutting the journey time in half. A similar road to New Smyrna was finished by 1905. On oceanside, a marled road led to the hard beach sands where automobile races became popular after 1902, and another linked Ormond to Seabreeze (Fitzgerald, 1937). Postcards of the period feature smooth brown roads painted in such a way to indicate aesthetic and reassuring durability.

THE DIXIE HIGHWAY

While part of the impetus to build roads for the new automobile led to a clearing and improvement of the King's Road, it would be the Dixie Highway (see Figure 3) a few years later that would change Volusia permanently, bringing mass tourism by automobile instead of simply elite winter vacationers and encouraging the development of the more sensitive wetland regions of the Halifax to accommodate and entertain tourists. The Dixie Highway also incentivized branch routes to the various St. Johns River and western Volusia communities.

The Dixie Highway was conceived by cycling and automobile entrepreneur Carl G. Fisher and his associate William Gilbreath. It formed part of a national 'Good Roads Movement' whose goal was to bring better cross-country highways at a time when increasingly affordable automobiles opened up travel opportunities to the middle class. Not all Floridians bought into the idea. Despite the poor and sometimes destructive conditions of rural roads in Florida (Ingram, 2014), few in rural Florida could yet afford an automobile at the time of construction. In any case, better roads meant more vehicles to upset livestock, more outside interference in close-knit rural communities, and higher taxes for what were seen as urban problems (Berger, 1979). However, resistance seems to have been worn down by a southern concern to improve their own local roads before governments chose which towns would be on the new routes and where mail would be delivered under the new postal regulations first implemented after 1918 that required drivable roads. There was also the attraction of easier and less muddy market roads (Preston, 1991; Proceedings Fourth American Road Congress, 1915). Nonetheless, progress was slow, as no strong federal inclination yet existed to fund roadbuilding in the south.

Figure 3: The Dixie Highway at completion in 1929. Source: Carl Fisher Papers, Box 4, Folder 46: “Dixie Highway,” History Miami, Miami, Fla.

Another cause for concern among Florida communities was the lack of local funding for construction. While the preferred materials for road building during the Good Roads Movement were brick and concrete, Florida communities could rarely afford large stretches in these expensive materials. Both had to be manufactured and hauled which, in a classic catch-22 situation, needed good roads to be able to do so. One solution used further north was to use a local sand and clay mixture. Once combined and then liquified to a mud, a sand/clay mortar can be sunbaked to a hardness that lasts years with little impact on the environment (FHA, n.d.). As most of Florida did not have abundant quantities of clay, some communities substituted bitumen oil, a poorer binder available from southern lakes and needing to be renewed frequently. The mixture also increased pollutant runoff when the rains washed the oil into the local streams and farmland (*Courier-Informant*, 1914). It did, however, keep the dust down and prevented water from seeping into the road base and undermining the road.

The Halifax area was not an oil producer and continued to use shell and gravel roads. Quarrying local Anastasia Formation Coquina for road surfaces was backbreaking work, and convict labor was contracted for the task. Bound in a sand and Calcite matrix, the Anastasia coquina was durable if friable over time. Coquina was also quarried in the Thompson/Bulow Creek area (Liston, 1996), although Volusia increasingly turned north to Flagler County for its supply. The superior quality Ocala limestone was preferred for aggregate, but at first it was prohibitively expensive as it had to be hauled overland. Nonetheless it would be used by wealthier Florida communities for road and building construction.

Extraction of both coquina and limestone began with the clearing of the overburden cover of earth. Explosives would then be set in most cases to break the rock for extraction and crushing before shipment to road crews (Ingram, 2014). No reclamation of quarries occurred when a lode was exhausted. The gravel or coquina, once delivered to road crews, would be laid by truck or mule-drawn equipment on the raised and levelled bed and tamped into place. Horseless trucks were still fairly new when the Dixie Highway was built (SLAF, 12302).

For the Halifax region, the Dixie Highway story picks up in April 1915 when the governors of several southern states convened in Chattanooga, Tennessee to discuss the merits of the proposed highway originally planned to link Indianapolis (not by coincidence Fisher's original home) to Miami (again not by coincidence Fisher's winter home). There was so much rancor among the governors and the Highway promoters over the route that one observer called it the "Second Battle of Chattanooga". Florida Governor Park Trammell decided not to wade into the politically charged fray, but his representatives negotiated routes along the east coast and through the center of the state, satisfying those who wanted the Dixie Highway routed through Atlanta and Jacksonville (*Atlanta Constitution*, 1915). Despite Tampa's efforts, Orlando deftly won over the commission in its bid to open up the farmlands of the state's spine to the proposed highway. Miami, at this time still a remote tropical rail destination, would now be linked more affordably to the rest of the state through a coastal trunk planned to run down from Jacksonville. These decisions had a massive impact on the Halifax region. Mindful of the benefits more roads like the Dixie Highway could bring and without funding to build them, Florida finally created a State Road Department in 1915 (Berry, 1923). Consequently, the road from Daytona to DeLand was marled, while brick lined streets appeared in DeLand and Daytona over the next decade (Hebel, 1955).

Designing Florida's roads was one thing, willingly paying for them was another. Southern states typically spent half of what northern states allotted for roads (Ingram, 2014). Roads remained

costly in Florida because of the extensive hardwood forests and wetlands, which is one reason there was heavy reliance on inexpensive convict labor (Gordon, 2017). Volusia County used predominantly Black convict chain-gangs, who did the work of slaves in conditions worse than had existed in antebellum Florida. The program was presented as a progressive and paternalist gesture for those who needed to pay their debt to society. However, Jim Crow racism created miserable conditions for Black convicts working on the Dixie Highway, a road whose very name came from a southern commemoration of the fiftieth anniversary of the Civil War (Gordon, 2017). Because these gangs were county-supervised, there was little state or federal oversight on working conditions, but also little interest to do so as the labor was cheap and the work force predominantly Black (Ingram, 2014; Preston, 1991). One author describes the labor and health conditions in Florida for state prisoners working on roads and phosphate mines as a 'hell-hole', a finding confirmed by several governmental investigations up through 1919 and later when Black convicts were diverted to other road projects (Kendrick, 1964). Construction camps operated between nine to fourteen months, and then rebuilt every ten to twenty miles, creating large areas temporarily worn down by human and mule occupation but eventually reclaimed by forest.

A March 1917 photograph of one such convict chain gang working on an unspecified section of the Daytona Road illustrates the difficulties of setting an improved road in central Florida (Figure 4). The forest cover that can be seen to either side of the road in older pictures of Volusia roads is absent, replaced by broad clearings and significant soil waste. The clearing reaches into wetlands, and the roadbed is raised. In this and other contemporary photographs the damage being done to wetlands and forests was extensive. Where bitumen had begun to be used there was runoff into wetlands, although the amount of automotive traffic on the Dixie Highway was still too small for overload of hydrocarbon pollution to build up.

Figure 4: Convict chain gang working on Volusia County section of Dixie Highway, ca 1917. State Library and Archives of Florida, photo number RC10401.

By 1919, authorities diverted convict chain gang labor to other projects, but roadbuilding continued in the Halifax region because of the federal 1916 Road Act, which provided \$75 million over five years to improve rural roads nationally for potential troop movements and economic development (Ingram, 2014; Seely, 1987). Florida was assured about \$1 million in annual funding and, like other southern states, used various taxes to match federal funds, most successfully gas and property tax increases. Given the dramatic increase in tourism by 1912, gas taxes were an effective funding mechanism as it captured revenue from those out of state as well as Florida residents.

TOURISM AND THE GROWTH OF DAYTONA

With better roads came more tourists, the great majority from the north seeking an outdoor and low-cost vacation in a national 1920s trend called autocamping (Preston, 1991). Autocamping was as it sounds: a combination of tents and cars promising freedom from stuffy hotels and dress codes and the chance to be a vagabond and meet interesting people. The wealthy also autocamped on occasion, albeit with better tents and Rolls Royces, to mingle with ‘Main Street’ (Belasco, 1979). While at first ‘tin-can tourists’ camped by the side of a road, the rising popularity of autocamping created issues of overcrowding in convenient spaces to the dismay of private landowners (SLAF, https://www.floridamemory.com/learn/exhibits/photo_exhibits/tincans/). Damage to the roadside was relatively minimal in the early days of autocamping, but eventually waste management issues became a pressing challenge. Local governments, anxious to control the issue without

stopping middle-class tourism, established public autocamp parks. In 1921 there were 38 established autocamps in Florida. By 1925 the number had grown to 210 locally funded autocampgrounds in Florida alone that promised better tents, amenities, groceries, entertainment, and safety for an average of 50-60 cars per day (Belasco, 1979). Most of those in Volusia County followed the Dixie Highway or Daytona to DeLand Road.

Autocamps provided better and cleaner facilities, but also more concentrated waste which would often end up in local wetlands. Trash was better managed at centralized autocamps, but still needed a mass disposal system (Berger, 1979). A 1922 notice in the national *Public Works Review* noted a paper recently read by George Simons, Florida's chief sanitary engineer, concerning the need to ensure a clean water supply and areas for human and other waste disposal, and the uneven local response to waste and hygiene. There was also the issue of the semi-permanent auto camper, the homeless down-at-heels or seasonal worker groups that auto camped by necessity and supposedly created huge waste disposal problems by imposing a constant and concentrated load on the facilities. For most communities, however, the increased load on the landscape was less an issue than the concern that the presence of the dilapidated worker vehicles quite bluntly ruined the 'look' of a campground designed for the casual 'vagabond' with spending money (Belasco, 1979). Florida law enforcement stopped "hitch-hiking, rod-riding, and flivver-driving itinerants" (sic) at the border; many of those turned back were African American (Snyder, 2002).

One early attempt at a solution to the waste management problem was mandating fees for campgrounds, the solution favored in Volusia County (Brown, 1924). The autocamps enjoyed a frenzied popularity until the 1930s, when cleaner private motor-hotels (motels) and cabins began to replace the camps despite improvements in tin-canners' camping equipment (https://www.floridamemory.com/learn/exhibits/photo_exhibits/tincans/).

While Ormond became a playground for the wealthy, tourism in 1920s Daytona catered to the middle-class. The towns of the Halifax were easily reachable by new roads and offered several amusements and expeditions that the middle-class pocketbook could afford. By 1919, 22 hotels, many on the beach, served nearly 2000 people per night (*Florida Times-Union*, 1919-1920). Daytona promoted itself as Florida's equivalent of Atlantic City or an American Riviera, attracting over 100,000 visitors each winter. On January 1, 1926, Daytona was incorporated into Daytona Beach, combining the oceanside town of Daytona Beach with Seabreeze and Daytona into a thirty-eight square mile region of 30,000 residents and named streets (Weaver, 2011; HHS, 1998.41). Various new developments and subdivisions required an expansion of the road system and a reappraisal of

the Halifax bridges. An active Park Board of Advisors staffed by the influential ladies of town worked to keep the streets and parks beautiful and sign free. The Daytona Beach Realty Board slogan was clear: “The Fountain of Youth is not IN Florida, the Fountain of Youth IS Florida” (HHS, C.M. Wilder Box, 1926-31).

Much of this new development was meant for a mobile middle class looking for a sunshine life, but other neighborhoods were populated by the large body of African Americans who had been pushed out of desirable Daytona areas since 1900. Previously, prosperous black merchants lived in Daytona in unsegregated neighborhoods, but segregated black neighborhoods formed west of the railroad tracks after 1900 (Lempel, 2001). These neighborhoods saw less attention to street improvement than in Daytona, and monies originally slated for drainage ditches and paving in Black neighborhoods were diverted to oceanside recreational areas (Snyder, 2002). Many Black residents arrived with the railways when the great citrus groves froze in the 1890s (Liston, 1996). By 1930 the significant African American community comprised one-third of Daytona’s population (Snyder, 2002; WPA 1939). These communities provided labor to work the outlying farms and to build the paradise Daytona and Ormond promoted to northern white families. They staffed the hotels and other tourist facilities but had to find their way to work by cart or bicycle. Cars remained out of reach for many African Americans, but a few fortunate Black residents of the area could buy their own automobiles and participate in a limited fashion in the freedom of the road (Gordon, 2017; Snyder, 2002).

As tourism was essential to the growth of the Halifax area, especially after the citrus freezes at the end of the nineteenth century made a produce economy risky, officials prioritized making Daytona attractive to visitors. Street expansion was also emphasized to attract permanent residents. Marketing Daytona as an accessible paradise depended on advertising a modern and accessible town with the charms of a local beach and the lush and beautiful Halifax, still teeming with fish, dolphins, and birds.

Clifton Johnson’s 1918 travelogue described the oceanside of the Halifax watershed as a combination of hardwood forest and saw palmetto (Johnson, 1918), but that picture would change rapidly over the next ten years. With increased speculation and subdivision development came the need for more streets and clearing in what had been a wet forest hammock. In some Volusia towns, the population doubled from 1910-1920 (Schene, 1976). Urban maps of the Halifax watershed suggest a well-defined transportation grid. A canal had been constructed west of Fourth Street to provide drainage for further agricultural and residential development. Then, during the ‘Great

Florida Land Boom of 1921-25', residential subdivision, hotel building, and street development accelerated on both sides of the river (Kendrick, 1964). The Main Street Bridge was completely replaced with a heartwood, creosote pine, and steel span after 1923, an expensive undertaking that underscored the wealth now invested in improving roads (HHS, C.M. Rogers Box, 1923). Major roads acquired hard surfaces and Halifax Drive (State Highway A1A by 1927) became the primary artery oceanside (Weaver, 2011). Firm and sturdy, beach roads remained popular in Volusia County (Johnson, 1918), but by the 1920s beach access roads showed wear and sand pollution, although a tourist-friendly postcard created from a gritty photograph (see Figures 5 and 6) shows the same scene as smooth and perfect (SLAF, 165137; 259433).

Figure 5: Beach road erosion on approach to Daytona Beach, undated but in 1920s. Source: State Library and Archives of Florida, photo number PHA038.

Figure 6: Postcard rendering of scene in Figure 5. Source: State Library and Archives of Florida, image number PC07512.

The boom created a rush to develop all along Florida's east coast, and land speculation was rife. Passengers and cargo competed for space on railroads, making the 1920s especially challenging to the railway industry. Miami was especially snarled. Cars loaded with excess building materials to feed the development boom were unable to unload until the empty cars of recently arrived prior trains could be removed. The rails needed constant maintenance. In late 1925 the Florida East Coast Railway declared a railroad embargo on all construction materials, stimulating maritime shipping until the rails could be expanded (Weaver, 2011; WPA, 1939). The embargo also helped cool the rampant speculation and development of land by 1926. Notable hurricanes in the 1920s ended the Great Florida Land Boom.

Railroads provided powerful incentives to build more roads as well. Freight moving via ports and Flagler's trains needed smooth access roads, and the industry subsidized those access points. Truckers on short-haul trips and other drivers took advantage of these well-built conduits that cost less than taking the railroad, reducing train congestion resulting from boom period developments that snarled the rail supply lines and damaged the trust in train haulage of Florida perishables

(especially citrus, the main product of the Halifax area at this time) (Ingram, 2014; MacDonald, 1932).

With the installation of cooling facilities at shipping terminals, trucks were able to make the short hauls into communities that the railroad and cargo ships could not reach. By 1937, Florida enacted legislation allowing rail lines to operate delivery trucks. In Daytona, a hard-surface truck route was constructed on what is now Nova Road (Hebel, 1955). On the human side, long distance passenger buses allowed flexible entry into many communities, which helped spur tourism and residential growth. In both cases, durable roads with permanent surfaces were the answer to the far less accessible rails (WPA 1939).

DAYTONA TRANSIT 1930-1970

With the resurgence of Daytona Beach tourism in the mid-1930s came asphalted city streets and the completion of U.S. Highway 1, which made access to Daytona from the north even easier (SLAF, 274238; compared to 259330 and 30712; Weaver, 2011). A 1925 mileage map of the best roads in Florida indicates an easy connection on U.S. Highway 92 of twenty-one miles between Daytona and DeLand en route to Kissimmee, the so-called 'Jackson Highway'. The same map also indicated that there was an offshoot from the Dixie Highway/Spanish Trail, the 'Atlantic Highway', accessible from Bunnell to Flagler Beach and continuing south (SLAF, 323012).

By 1939, authors of the Works Progress Administration's *Florida: A Guide to the Southernmost State* noted a railway station, two passenger bus terminals, and a municipal airport in the town of Daytona, which it described as a thriving town of over 16,000 (WPA, 1939). A large gas station on Main Street had opened two years previously by mechanic Bill France, who took advantage of the lack of fueling stations on the barrier island (Weaver, 2011). Already possessed of 39 hotels and many more bed-and-breakfasts called 'tourist houses', Daytona also boasted four full golf courses, five picture houses, and several community events. Most permanent residents lived on the west side of the Halifax, while the four permanent bridges across the river allowed access to a growing permanent and wealthy residential community beachside.

There was a downside. Despite continued narrative and painted depictions of the Halifax area as paradise (MOAS, 002276), WPA writers noted the disappearance of local vegetation. While commenting on the region's lushness, writers mentioned that the live oak, magnolia and bay trees that once marked prolific hardwood forests in the area now merely lined the streets. Postcards from the 1930s placed heavy emphasis on drivable beaches and the Halifax area as an automobile mecca.

Added to this was the initiation of Bike Week beginning in 1937, drawing hundreds of motorcyclists to the beaches every spring. Already the beaches had issues with exhaust and motor oil. While scientific records do not go back far enough to verify, photographs suggest that sea turtle nesting was disrupted in the area. Since the 1930s, the steady growth of hard surface roads and cars in the region had a continuing and growing impact on urban runoff in the watershed, dune and dune grass erosion, roadside degradation, and bank erosion near bridges.

The final episode in roadbuilding addressed here is the completion of U.S. Highway 1 and Interstate Highways 95 and 4. The section of the Dixie Highway that crossed Volusia County was essentially absorbed into U.S. Highway 1. By this time, asphalt-concrete amalgams were preferred, creating environmental run-off issues (Kendrick, 1964). The completion of the Florida Turnpike in the early 1960s served as the impetus for a connector highway from Interstate Highway 95 in Daytona to Orlando and Tampa. Interstate 4 was completed in 1964, while Interstate 95 was completed in Daytona by 1970. The Dixie Highway faded into oblivion in the Halifax region, but the name has been retained on a section of U.S. 1 running from the mouth of the Tomoka River in Ormond along Bulow Creek Park to Plantation Bay.

Interstate 95 would have repercussions on the St. Johns watershed. By diverting north/south traffic from U.S. Highway 17 in western Volusia County, several older towns like Pierson, Crescent City, and Satsuma faded in prominence on what had been historically the most used route to Jacksonville in central Florida. Development moved from west of the St. Johns River to the eastern Florida shoreline. Ironically, this allowed much of the central route to remain rooted in agriculture, with less road damage.

Finally, the popularity of Daytona Beach would be a major factor in the creation of a permanent airport in 1930, with full passenger service beginning in 1946. The region had been a frontier for flight because the same hard beaches that attracted automobile races also proved useful as a runway for early airplanes, aerial entertainment, and mail runs. The 1920s Cowan's Beach Airport attracted early aviators including Clarence Chamberlin, the first man to take a passenger across the Atlantic to Berlin (SLAF, 6791). By 1928, the city created an airport at Bethune Point, but the site was hazardous and at times fatal during take-off; the airport was moved to its present site in 1930. The runways were paved with coquina, which coincidentally absorbed most of the fuel oil. After 1946, air travel surpassed rail travel as the preferred means to reach Daytona, and the city began construction of a full terminal by 1952. By the end of the decade the airport handled over 6,000

flights per year, prompting increased investments in terminals and other facilities. Road building accelerated as the Halifax watershed became increasingly accessible by air and hotel demand grew.

CONCLUSIONS

Up until the 1880s, roads had very little impact on the natural landscape of the Halifax basin. Even relatively well-built historic roads like the King's Road cast a minimal footprint on the semi-tropical forests. The structures left behind by the English, Spanish, and pre-Seminole American settlers faded so easily into the forest that, by the 1880s, few remembered them or could locate and identify the ruins (e.g. James Ormond III went for a search of his childhood home Damietta in the early 1880s, and found only one chimney). Given the landscape, environmental conditions, and available technology of the time, it is little wonder that older roads most often faded back into the wetlands and forests with very little trace (Liston, 1996).

This minimal impact changed dramatically with increased settlement in the Ormond and Daytona areas and the introduction of the railroad. The demand for construction lumber and timbers for the rails and bridges scarred the forests closest to the Halifax, while coal spillage impacted wetlands. The introduction of oil/sand and shell roads to service the needs of automobiles accelerated local coquina quarrying, while contemporary studies of hydrocarbon pollution in Volusia County strongly suggest that the less regulated road building and use introduced new petrol-based runoff from the roadbeds as well as exhaust in the forests (see for example Kheimi et al., 2022 and Goolsby et al., 2016). The Dixie Highway gave average tourists access to all of the Daytona attractions previously reserved for winter elites, and Daytona promoted itself as an affordable tropical town with northern travel amenities. The resulting exponential growth of Daytona Beach and Ormond as tourist and residential destinations in the early twentieth century accelerated roadbuilding and bridge construction, stressing the popular but environmentally fragile beach access, damaging riverbanks, and reducing forests and wetlands. Finally, the construction of interstate highways and a full airport in the mid-twentieth century so urbanized the landscape that the lush natural environment that had attracted settlers and magnates a century before was reduced to modified fringe vegetation, parkland, and reserves. Today, the Halifax River Urban Watershed is a child of Daytona's marketed appeal as an accessible paradise for those who loved to be behind the wheel.

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PHOTO ESSAY:

Plantations, Wars, and the Ruins: Historical Components Shaping the Halifax River Basin

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ABSTRACT

The establishment of sugar plantations in the Halifax region of Northeast Florida during the territorial era between 1821 and 1845 was significant both historically and environmentally. Sugar plantations in the Halifax region proved to be a profitable industry, albeit with a heavy reliance on enslaved people to help meet the increased demand for labor. Establishing plantations, however, resulted in significant impacts on the natural environment, including alterations to ecosystems, land-use patterns, topography, vegetation, and water quality. The Second Seminole War (1835-1842) destroyed many of these plantations, impacting the region and shaping the future social, economic, and environmental history of Northeast Florida. This photo essay reviews the visible remains of plantations and the associated past conflicts within the Halifax River region (Eastern parts of Volusia and Flagler Counties) during the early stages of the territorial era in Florida, encompassing the years between 1821 and 1845. The historic sites noted in this paper are available for public access. The photographs are accompanied with a narrative by Zach Zacharies, the Senior Curator of History at the Museum of Arts and Science of Daytona Beach, Florida.

Keywords: plantations, sugar mills, Seminole wars, ruins, Halifax River basin

SUGAR MILL PLANTATIONS AND THEIR IMPACTS ON ENVIRONMENT

The Halifax River region was known for its fertile soil and suitable climate for growing sugarcane, which attracted many planters to the area. The plantations were located in areas with suitable soil and climatic conditions, and the presence of rivers and streams was an essential factor for irrigation and transportation (Figure 1). The plantations in the Halifax region of Northeast Florida represented a significant land-use change during the colonial period.

Figure 1. Natural waterway where Halifax River and Tomoka River meet. Ormond Beach, Florida. The presence of rivers and streams was an essential factor for irrigation and transportation. Photograph by Hyun Jung Cho, November 29, 2021.

A significant influx of primarily Anglo-Celtic settlers migrated to the region with the primary intention of cultivating highly profitable cash crops, specifically sugarcane. The establishment of sugar plantations in the Halifax region of northeast Florida proved to be particularly profitable, leading to a rapid expansion of the industry and a corresponding increase in demand for labor. These planters relied heavily on enslaved people to meet the demand for labor to cultivate, harvest, and process their sugarcane crops, making slavery a significant aspect of the Halifax region's sugar plantations in the 1830s (Figure 2).

Slavery in the Halifax region was not only a brutal system of exploitation but also a deeply entrenched social and economic institution. Enslaved people had no legal rights, and their lives were subject to the whims of their owners. Yet enslaved people played a critical role in the success of the sugar industry, and slave labor was essential to the profitability of the region's sugar plantations until the destruction of the plantations during the Second Seminole War.

Figure 2. The establishment of sugar plantations proved to be particularly profitable, leading to a rapid expansion of the industry and a corresponding increase in demand for slave labor. Photograph of display at the Bulow Plantation Ruins Historic State Park by Hyun Jung Cho, December 18, 2021.

The establishment of these plantations altered the natural environment and had significant impacts on the surrounding ecosystems, water resources, and land use patterns (Figure 3). To begin with, the establishment of plantations required extensive land clearing, draining, and modification of the natural environment to support agricultural activities. The planters employed methods such as deforestation, drainage, and ditching to create fields and access roads. These activities altered the topography, hydrology, and vegetation of the area, leading to soil erosion, siltation, and changes in water quality. The introduction of exotic plant species such as sugarcane and citrus trees also altered the local ecosystem, replacing the native vegetation and changing the food web. The management of waste and the disposal of human excreta and other organic agricultural and domestic wastes most likely led to the contamination of soil and water resources.

Figure 3. Cruger-dePeyster Plantation Sugar Mill Ruins in New Smyrna Beach, FL. The plantations in the Halifax region of northeast Florida represented a significant land-use change during the colonial period. Photograph by Hyun Jung Cho, November 25, 2021.

THE SECOND SEMINOLE WAR AND PLANTATIONS

The Halifax sugar plantations and their enslaved populations ended with the Second Seminole War (1835-1842), a prolonged and disastrous conflict between the United States and the Seminole people (who resisted relocation to Oklahoma) that resulted in no true peace accord. Unlike the First Seminole War, which took place primarily in the Florida panhandle, the Second Seminole War was waged in east-central Florida along the St. Johns River and what is now the Intracoastal Waterway—including the Halifax River. There were major engagements in the Second Seminole War with well over a dozen sugar mill plantations destroyed at the beginning of the conflict. Chief Osceola, while not an official chief, initiated the war by directing attacks on numerous sugar plantations from St. Augustine to New Smyrna Beach, resulting in several Seminole victories in pitched battles.

During the conflict, Major Benjamin Putnam and his militia, known as the “Mosquito Roarers,” seized the largest and most profitable plantation, Bulowville (Figure 4). John Joachim Bulow, who inherited the plantation after the death of his father Wilhelm, maintained amicable relations with the local Seminoles. When the militia arrived, Bulow fired a small cannon at them and was subsequently held prisoner on his own property. The plantation became known as Bulow Station and was fortified as a defensive position. In January 1835, the militia ordered an evacuation of Bulow Station, and all refugees fled to St. Augustine. John Bulow left his plantation as a prisoner of war and died a few years later in St. Augustine. The Seminoles destroyed Bulowville, including the factory and the coquina main house. Today, Bulow Plantation Ruins State Historic Park, with its visible factory ruins and wells provides visitors with a ghostly glimpse of the site’s past.

Figure 4. Bulow Plantation Ruins State Historic Park, Flagler Beach, Florida. Photographs by Hyun Jung Cho, December 18, 2021

General Joseph Hernandez, a Florida native who became a soldier, politician, and plantation owner, led the Florida militia. He ordered soldiers to head south to a plantation at the present-day Dunlawton Sugar Mill Gardens, where they encountered the Seminoles who had already destroyed and burned the mill (Figure 5). A skirmish ensued, referred to as the “Battle of Dunlawton,” in which the Seminoles led by Coacoochee (Wildcat) greatly outnumbered and ambushed the militia. The Mosquito Roarers were undisciplined and inexperienced in combat, and their retreat to Bulow Station resulted in four dead and fourteen wounded.

Figure 5. Sugar mill ruins at Dunlawton, Port Orange, Florida. It is a Volusia County Park and maintained by a non-profit volunteer group called Botanical Gardens of Volusia, Inc. Photographs by Hyun Jung Cho, November 14, 2021.

Other plantations, such as the Cruger-dePeyster Sugar Mill and Dummett's Carrickfergus, were also destroyed by the Seminoles (Figures 6 and 7). Initially mistaken as a Spanish mission by earlier historians, archaeological investigations have established the true function of Cruger-dePeyster as a sugar mill factory. The plantation was established by William Cruger and Henry dePeyster, who acquired 600 acres of land to cultivate sugarcane. However, the enterprise lasted only five years as Seminole warriors attacked and destroyed the plantation in 1835. The enslaved individuals belonging to Cruger-dePeyster assisted the Seminoles in destroying the property. Despite the passage of time, the ruins of the Cruger-dePeyster Sugar Mill still exist, albeit in a state of deterioration due to the challenging Florida environment, rampant vegetation growth, and damage caused by the removal of coquina stone. Notably, the remnants of the plantation bear evidence of the devastating fires set by the Seminoles during the Second Seminole War, as discernible burn marks are still evident on the coquina walls.

Figure 6. Cruger-dePeyster Plantation Sugar Mill Ruins in New Smyrna Beach, FL. Photograph by Hyun Jung Cho, November 14, 2021.

The Dummett Ruins, situated south of Bulowville roughly one mile to the west of the entrance to Tomoka State Park, is an intriguing archaeological site that merits exploration. This site is the former location of a sugar mill plantation named Carrickfergus, owned and operated by British Marine Officer Colonel Thomas Dummett. The plantation was operated by a workforce of approximately 200 enslaved Africans and was renowned for being the first steam-powered sugar mill in the Halifax region. However, in 1835, Seminole warriors destroyed the plantation. Visitors can access the site through a small parking area and can view the crumbling ruins from a designated fenced-in area. The historical significance of the Dummett Ruins as the location of an early steam-powered sugar mill and its association with the lives and labor of enslaved individuals adds further weight to its importance as an archaeological and historical site.

Figure 7. Dummett Sugar Mill Ruins in Tomoka State Park, Ormond Beach, FL. Photograph by Hyun Jung Cho, April 5, 2020.

The Mala Compra plantation, formerly owned by General Joseph Hernandez, represents an important site of historical and cultural significance (Figure 8). Born in St. Augustine in 1788, Hernandez became a brigadier general and a U.S. Territorial Member of Congress representing

Florida. He was the first Hispanic to serve in Congress and sat on the committee responsible for selecting Tallahassee as the state capital. Hernandez purchased the 800-acre Mala Compra plantation in 1816 while Florida was still under Spanish rule, choosing to remain there following the transition to U.S. ownership. Situated on the east bank of the Matanzas River in Flagler County at a location known as Bing's Landing, Mala Compra is noteworthy for being the only plantation situated on a barrier island.

The plantation operations at Mala Compra were diverse, with the cultivation of sea island cotton and oranges being the primary crops. These activities had a significant impact on the land, and archaeological studies have revealed evidence of the extensive modifications made to the natural environment to support the plantation's activities. In 1835, the plantation was converted into a military post by the U.S. government, and roughly 80 enslaved individuals worked the land. However, when the Seminole people attacked in 1836 the plantation had already been evacuated of army personnel, and the plantation house and support buildings were destroyed. Although the Seminoles were able to capture three of the enslaved individuals, the rest had apparently dispersed into the surrounding area. Mala Compra has been studied by archaeologists and is well-preserved, *with a large pavilion protecting the excavated site and offering an award-winning interpretation of its historical significance.

Most of the plantations destroyed during the Seminole Wars are inaccessible to the public or have been lost to time, but the region encompassing Volusia and Flagler County in the Halifax area of Florida is privileged to possess one of the most substantial plantation sites dating back to the Spanish and territorial periods in Florida. Mala Compra and the several other sites mentioned here provide unique opportunities to engage with the history of the Second Seminole War and to appreciate the legacy of the enslaved individuals who labored on these plantations. In addition, several of these sites offer public access, providing opportunities for the broader community to engage with the region's rich cultural heritage. The loss or destruction of any cultural heritage site represents a critical loss of evidence regarding what it means to be human, highlighting the value of preserving such sites for future generations.

Figure 8. The Mala Compra Plantation, Palm Coast, Florida (image source: <https://www.visitflorida.com/>)

The Timucua, Traditional Environmental Knowledge, and the Possibility of Restorative Justice in the Halifax River Urban Watershed

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ABSTRACT

The Timucua were an Indigenous people who lived in what is now southern Georgia and northern Florida, including the Halifax River watershed. A relatively settled and thriving culture in the region, they tended to remain in the same location for extended periods, assumedly gaining extensive knowledge of their inhabited areas. Today, no remaining members of this culture are among us as they all but disappeared by 1763, primarily from exposure to diseases brought by Europeans who settled the area beginning in the sixteenth century. Morally, when encountering an injustice, addressing that injustice is the ethical response. However, the specified injustice to the Timucua people occurred hundreds of years ago, was arguably unintentional, and none of those who experienced it remain. Given this situation, restorative justice (very different from retributive justice) is a procedure that can lead to a recognition of how justice, in some way, can still be done. From the perspective of restorative justice, working toward the robust inclusion of traditional (indigenous) environmental knowledge to the extent that it exists might represent the best that can be done, might illustrate a response to the historic harm, and at the same time might also generate a fuller understanding of the watershed. Thus, the inclusion of traditional environmental knowledge into the study of the Halifax River watershed might represent a sound and just response in light of the harms that the Timucua faced so long ago.

Keywords: Halifax River, restorative justice, Timucua, traditional environmental knowledge

INTRODUCTION

This is an article about restorative justice and its application to a tragic (and unjust) occurrence in the history of what is now known as the Halifax River urban watershed. Here, I am referring to the disappearance of the Timucua, a people who once lived and thrived in the region. No remaining members of this culture are among us as they all but disappeared by 1763 primarily from exposure to diseases brought by Europeans who settled the area beginning in the sixteenth century (Milanich 1996).

The Timucua were an Indigenous people who lived in what is now southern Georgia and northern Florida, including the Halifax River watershed. Rather than migrating frequently from place to place, they tended to remain in the same location for extended periods of time. The Timucua hunted, fished, gathered resources to sustain their communities and presumably had extensive knowledge of their surroundings including waterways (Milanich, 1996).

Morally, when faced with an injustice, doing justice is the ethical response. Yet, the injustice I have specified here occurred hundreds of years ago, was arguably not intentional, and none of those who experienced it remain. How then can justice be done?

THE LIMITS OF RETRIBUTIVE JUSTICE

In conventional terms, doing justice often entails accusing a particular person or persons of wrongdoing. Evidence is then gathered, and an assessment made regarding any guilt or liability on the part of those accused, and if found guilty or liable some sort of sanction is applied. This process, known as retributive justice, seems ill equipped to address the injustice directed at the Timucua. After all, one might say that this harm happened centuries ago and involved people who are no longer with us. How could a sense of moral responsibility or doing justice apply when considering a harm so far in the past, particularly when no one at present can reasonably be accused of having done any wrongdoing? Moreover, it also seems self-evident that, while the Timucua were ravaged by European diseases, nothing in this suggests that those who settled from Europe intended for this to happen. One might therefore conclude that the loss of an entire culture is morally wrong but is ‘water under the bridge,’ as one might say, and beyond the identification of a historically relevant harm, so little more can or need be done.

As I will elaborate in what follows, restorative justice, a process that entails a procedure very different from retributive justice, leads to a recognition of how justice, in some way, can still be done. To support how this is so, it is first necessary to define what restorative justice is and describe how it

functions. As will soon become evident, the focus of restorative justice is very different from retributive justice, and what doing restorative justice entails is very different as well. Following from an understanding of what restorative justice is and how it is performed, I will then offer a concrete suggestion about what doing justice might entail in response to the fate of the Timucua.

RESTORATIVE JUSTICE

We contend that there is another kind of justice, restorative justice, which was characteristic of traditional African jurisprudence. Here the central concern is not retribution or punishment. In the spirit of ubuntu, the central concern is the healing of breaches, the redressing of imbalances, the restoration of broken relationships... (Tutu, 1999a).

Restorative justice is a system that focuses on those who have been harmed rather than those who did harm, and it involves addressing those harms in concrete ways. It offers the possibility for social reconciliation and solidarity (Tutu, 1999b). In working through a restorative process, one attempts to identify who was harmed, what the harm actually was, and what community was involved. The purpose is not to assign blame but to identify needs. The emphasis is to live rightly within the multiple relationships a person experiences, and understanding what living rightly means becomes apparent as the process unfolds. While admitting the importance of acting on principle, restorative justice also looks to the future as an intentional exercise focused on bringing forth the greatest level of well-being for those involved.

As Howard Zehr (2009) elaborates, in practicing restorative justice one assumes “when people and relationships are harmed, needs are created,” that “the needs created by harms lead to obligations,” and that those obligations lead to healing or “putting right” the harm. Doing so is considered a just response. Following from these assumptions, practicing restorative justice entails acting in ways that are consistent with three values, each of which frames a just response. As Zehr (2009) summarizes,

A just response acknowledges and repairs the harm caused by, and revealed by, wrongdoing (restoration); encourages appropriate responsibility for addressing needs and repairing the harm (accountability); [and] involves those impacted, including the community, in the resolution (engagement).

Restoration, accountability, and engagement suggest a great deal about what being responsible for doing justice entails.

LIABILITY vs. SOCIAL CONNECTION MODELS of RESPONSIBILITY

Iris Marion Young (2011a) argues convincingly that a suitable starting place in a discussion about doing justice is to first examine how injustice is experienced. She focuses on five interrelated understandings of injustice, naming marginalization, cultural imperialism, systematic violence, exploitation, and powerlessness as common experiences, each describing injustice as a personal and socio-structural concern. She further stresses that any moral imperative that follows from any of these forms of injustice arises from the presence of the injustice as an existential reality and not from any identification of a person or persons who can be, or should be, blamed. These injustices, in other words, matter because they exist and not because someone can be blamed for them.

Building on these ideas, Young (2011b) elaborates two understandings of responsibility that help illustrate the difference between retributive and restorative justice. She refers to these as the “Liability Model of Responsibility” and the “Social Connection Model of Responsibility.” In the case of the former, a person is held to account for their individual actions. She stresses the importance of recognizing responsibility in such terms, particularly for a society that values freedom. We are, in this view, responsible to and for ourselves. In the case of the latter, we are also responsible to and for one another. As Young (2011b, p.96) emphasizes,

The social connection model finds that all those who contribute by their actions to structural processes with some unjust outcomes share responsibility for the injustice. This responsibility is not primarily backward-looking, as the attribution of guilt or fault is, but rather primarily forward-looking. Being responsible in relation to structural injustice means that one has an obligation to join with others who share that responsibility in order to transform the structural processes to make their outcomes less unjust.

The Social Connection Model as she defines it consists of five elements or characteristics, each contrasting with the Liability Model. The first is a rejection of a process where the one who allegedly engaged in wrongdoing is seen separately, or in isolation, from their social context. In the Liability Model, a person is regarded in individual terms and is in a sense abstracted away from or out of the larger social circumstances or context within which their alleged actions took place. In contrast, the Social Connection Model begins with the view that those involved are interrelated. The wrongs that one might do to another are seen as situated within larger social contexts. This leads to the second characteristic of the Social Connection Model, namely, that this model focuses on judging background conditions. The social structures relating to both harms and actions intended to do justice are no less

focused upon than the actions of any one moral agent. In a sense then, as Young continues, the Social Connection Model is focused on problem solving and not “blame” and, as such, is “more forward looking than backward looking” (2011b, p.108). This orientation toward the future constitutes the third characteristic of the Social Connection Model, while suggesting the fourth: in doing justice, the Social Connection Model assumes a sense of “shared responsibility” (2011b, p.109). Finally, the fifth characteristic of the Social Connection Model is that doing justice becomes a matter of “collective action” (2011b, p.111). Young’s Liability Model corresponds to retributive justice. Contrastingly, restorative justice seems to correspond to the Social Connection Model of Responsibility.

Since restorative justice follows the Social Connection Model of Responsibility, the intentions of those who have done harm is not the issue. The harms done, identifiable in terms of injustice, are at issue because of their existence. The kinds of systematic injustices noted above are a focus of restorative justice even if those who did harm did not intend for harm to occur. Restorative justice applies to instances when a direct causal relationship exists between the harms done and those who did harm but also applies when this kind of direct causal relationship is not present. As Young (2011b, p.104) argues, “To the extent that we participate in the ongoing operations of a society in which injustice occurs, we ought to be held responsible.” She further suggests that (p.106),

In principle, moreover, structural injustice may be ongoing even when some of the participating actors have done nothing that existing practices of criminal, legal, or moral blame or fault-finding would identify as wrong. Those who participate by their actions in producing and reproducing structural injustice are usually minding their own business and acting within accepted norms and rules. They bear responsibility for unjust outcomes, which they may regret, without being specifically at fault. Thus finding that third parties bear responsibility, either in the sense that they have done an actionable harm or that they have contributed to unjust outcomes through their action within accepted institutional rules, does not absolve them (us) of responsibility as well.

CONNECTION TO THE TIMUCUA

As the forgoing suggests, doing justice in response to a harm that occurred a very long time ago cannot be a matter of assigning blame or personal liability. The fact that no person today had anything to do with what happened to the Timucua makes the notion of the Liability Model irrelevant and renders any sense of retributive justice moot. Similarly, the Liability Model does not apply to those who brought with them the diseases that unexpectedly ravaged the Timucua. Yet the Liability Model is not the only way to consider what acting in response to an injustice might mean. If

the question moves away from assigning blame and more toward a sense of shared responsibility and collective action for harms that have been done, the final two stages of the Social Connection Model of Responsibility, then might this suggest a role for restorative justice? If I am to speak of shared responsibility and collective action, how might that apply not only to those who live in the watershed now, but also to those lost long ago?

The harm I have identified (the disappearance of the Timucua) brings with it a varied sense of moral wrongs. The disappearance of the Timucua can be characterized as an instance of cultural imperialism and systematic violence. Perhaps what happened to the Timucua can in some way be addressed through present day collective action and shared responsibility. This seems especially the case when considering this harm in terms of cultural imperialism.

Surely, the Timucua knew something about the land they inhabited. Along with their disappearance is perhaps the concurrent disappearance of any knowledge they gained through their experience of the land and waterways of the Halifax River watershed. Acknowledging that possibility suggests a way to enact a sense of shared responsibility and collective action in the present.

Scientific inquiry is commonly defined by the employment of the scientific method and constitutes an important way to know about a place and the people who occupy that place. Science is central in any investigation of not only the Halifax River watershed but also the curricula used by upcoming environmental scientists, policy makers, and practitioners, all of whom are dedicating their professional lives to environmental protection and examining the larger environmental and social context of the Halifax River urban watershed. Yet, as Eric Higgs (2005) identified long ago, scientific inquiry (based as it is on the scientific method) does not fully address how one can know about a place and the people who occupy that place. Another possibility, perhaps less in the mainstream, is referred to as Traditional Environmental Knowledge (TEK). According to (Cleveland, 2009, p.318):

Humans have understood their environments in terms of traditional (or indigenous) ecological knowledge (TEK). TEK has been a major determinant of the ways in which people have interacted with their environment—for all peoples at some point in the past, and for many today as well, though much TEK has been lost via the diminution or disappearance of cultural groups, or greatly modified by interaction with scientific ecological knowledge (SEK), the knowledge generated by the more formal, organized investigation of the world that has become increasingly dominant.

Many have called for the integration of TEK for some time, including, among others, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) Working Group II (David-Chavez and Gavin,

2018). Yet, as Mazzocchi (2006) suggests, doing so is not an easy task. He cites possibilities for romanticizing indigenous cultures and not seeing them as heterogeneous constituencies that have not always had cooperative relations with the land. Moreover, as he suggests (p.464), “It is not possible to simply reduce [TEK] to practical knowledge that is exclusively based on experience as opposed to theoretical knowledge, which is developed through deductive or inductive reasoning.” Yet, he and many others argue for the inclusion of TEK, although not without careful and critical consideration.

The question for the Halifax River urban watershed, and for the research initiative of which this article is a part, is whether or not TEK exists for the watershed and, if so, how it might be more robustly included in gathering knowledge about the watershed and in curricula that prepares students for environmental work there? Would the inclusion of TEK, if available, be an initiative that would represent the employment of restorative justice?

Restorative justice focuses on harms as well as those who have been harmed. Clearly the Timucua are no longer with us and direct experience of their own TEK has been forever lost. Still, restorative justice promotes the righting of wrongs as best one can (and oftentimes, this cannot be fully accomplished).

At present, others may regard the loss of the Timucua as somewhat emblematic of their own contemporary experiences of marginalization or cultural imperialism. There may be forms of TEK that are known by other marginalized people who also happen to inhabit the Halifax River urban watershed today.

In a broader sense then, working toward the robust inclusion of TEK to the extent that it exists might represent the best that can be done, might illustrate a response to the harm done long ago, and at the same time might also generate a fuller understanding of the watershed. In short, the inclusion of TEK might be our best sound and just response in light of the harms that the Timucua faced so long ago.

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Urban Density Changes and Associated Flood Vulnerability in the Halifax River Watershed

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ABSTRACT

The Halifax River urban watershed is undergoing rapid socioeconomic changes that are interacting with natural hazards like coastal flooding driven by sea level rise. We employ a spatially explicit approach to examine changes in past and future land cover, explore the relationship with flooding associated with sea level rise, and discuss possible economic repercussions. We also make use of publicly accessible data related to land cover, population, and sea level rise projections to examine the potential for flooding associated with sea level to drive economic changes in the watershed. We predict significant development of land cover over time with more than 50 percent of the watershed potentially being developed in the next 50 years and about 1 to 13 percent of that development inundated if the current rate of sea level rise continues. When this development interacts with predicted sea level rise, there will be significant economic losses. This work can be leveraged to carry out larger-scale economic assessments in light of rapid urban sprawl and sea level rise.

Keywords: sea level rise, house price, Central Florida, tourism

INTRODUCTION

Background

The banks of the Halifax River are already heavily developed, and new developments are moving inland with an increasing density over time. But even with the new development and increased density, housing prices, fueled by a growing population, are rising rapidly. Increased hazard risk from sea level rise and more powerful hurricanes increase insurance costs, further increasing the cost of home ownership in Florida (Graff Zivin et al., 2020; Barrage and Furst, 2019; Bin et al., 2017). Perhaps surprisingly, the market response to natural disasters only results in temporary declines in housing prices as memories fade, new residents lack information on flood risk,

and damaged houses are replaced with newer, higher-valued construction (Graff Zivin et al., 2020; Bin and Landry, 2013; Hallstrom and Smith, 2005).

As we consider changes to the natural and manmade landscape, housing markets provide an important link between present conditions and the future. Housing accounts for approximately two-thirds of an average person's wealth while housing investments and services added 17% to the nation's GDP in 2020 (NAHB, 2022; Iacoviello, 2011). In Florida, housing markets are an important nexus among people, natural amenities, the built environment, jobs, and economic growth, as well as a source of current opportunities and future risks.

Socioeconomic Conditions and Housing Markets

With 404,266 net immigrants, more people moved into Florida in 2020-21 than moved away: a number exceeded only twice (1971 and 1972) in its history. Nevertheless, the Demographic Estimating Conference forecasts that Florida's population will grow more slowly in the future. As the elderly have become a larger share of Florida's population, natural population growth in the state (births minus deaths) turned negative in 2021 and population growth in Florida has been driven entirely by people moving to the state. The state's population growth in the future is projected to depend entirely on immigration, and growth rates are projected to fall to approximately half of current rates over the next 15 years, from 1.6% annually to 0.8% (FOEDR, 2022). Immigration thus plays an important role in Florida's housing market. The University of Florida's Bureau of Economic and Business Research projects the state's population will be 27.1 million in 2045, and 33.7 million in 2070, representing population increases of 26% and 53% respectively relative to 2020 (BEBR, 2022).

There is a debate in economics about whether immigrants respond to economic incentives such as wages, economic opportunity, low taxes, or to quality-of-life amenities such as a warm climate, outdoor activities, and inviting environmental features such as rivers and beaches (Partridge 2010). One reason that Florida has high numbers of immigrants is that it offers both economic opportunities and numerous amenities. Natural amenities in the region, in addition to climate, include beaches, rivers, springs, estuaries, forests, and coral reefs that are used by people for a variety of recreational activities including fishing, boating, diving, hunting, riding, hiking, and camping provided by one of the largest state park systems in the nation (Pienaar, 2017). Other important amenities in the region include sporting venues such as the Daytona International Speedway, and a multitude of theme parks (Disney World, Universal Studios, and Sea World among others). Because

many of Florida's newest residents are retirees, work incentives are likely to play a smaller part in their decision than climate, social networks, and other amenities. In addition, technological and social changes during the Covid pandemic have allowed many workers to telecommute or work from home, which also lessens the role of work incentives in choosing a place to live. We emphasize the role that amenities have in attracting Florida's record number of immigrants because, without careful land-use planning, high levels of housing growth can degrade the very amenities that attract residents to the region.

While migration patterns can be complex, several studies show Central Florida to be an attractive landing place for new residents – both migrants moving from out of state and in-state residents relocating to less-crowded, more affordable areas (Hauer 2017; Carr and Zwick, 2016). Immigrants are shown to drive up the value of houses not only where they settle but also in surrounding areas as local residents relocate in response to changing housing prices and population demographics (Mussa, 2017; Saiz, 2007). In addition, new residents spur the development of low-density subdivisions of single-family housing. Carr and Zwick (2016), in a study for 1000 Friends of Florida, find that agricultural lands and other green spaces in Central Florida could shrink by over 2.3 million acres by 2070 as half of all green spaces are replaced by developments. Climate change plays an important role in these projections. Hauer (2017) estimates that as many as 250,000 residents from South Florida will relocate to Central Florida due entirely to the impacts of future sea level rise. A separate study assessed Florida as second only to Louisiana in its vulnerability to wetland migration due to sea level rise (Osland et al., 2022). On the Atlantic coast, upland forests and upland croplands are the most vulnerable to urban sprawl, adding to the threats to existing inland natural systems as people have started to develop them (Osland et al., 2022).

Vulnerability to Coastal Flooding, Land Cover, and Housing Markets

Vulnerability to climatic hazards such as coastal flooding is generally a product of intensity of exposure to risks such as the extent and frequency of coastal flooding, sensitivity of the social and natural systems of the coast, the strength of the built environment to withstand such shocks, as well as access of the people living in those areas to social and economic resources (Chang and Huang, 2015; Adger, 2006). Flood vulnerability in Florida's coastal region is the product of rapidly increased coastal flooding driven by sea level rise as well as more frequent hurricanes and a rapid and unsustainable development of coastal regions (Shen et al., 2016). In the US, nearly 41 million people live within the 1% annual exceedance probability floodplain (sometimes called the 100-year

floodplain), with increasing numbers of people moving to flood prone regions (Wing et al., 2018). These changes in land use are exacerbated in Florida because of its rapid population growth rate.

The Halifax watershed is emblematic of Florida's rapid increase in urban sprawl. Natural areas are rapidly being developed into housing. At the same time, the price of housing has increased, driven by local as well as national demand, and insurance markets are in flux as they seek to assess the effects of increasing flood risk and other hazards from a changing climate. In this article, we aim to establish baseline information related to landcover change, sea level rise, and their interaction with the economic condition of the Halifax watershed. We also aim to explore the temporal dynamics of land cover change, sea level rise, housing prices, and their interaction.

METHODS

Study Area: Halifax River

The Halifax River lies in the north-eastern part of Volusia County in East-Central Florida. This river, a part of the Atlantic Intracoastal Waterway, is a linear estuary approximately 23 miles long and roughly a half mile wide on average. It flows along the City of Daytona Beach and the eastern coast of Volusia County in Central Florida (Cho and Reiter, 2020). We adopted the watershed approach to this study and included the entire huc10 (Hydrological Unit Code) watershed surrounding the Halifax River within Volusia County (Figure 1). The area next to the Halifax River is heavily urbanized and the areas further inland are being urbanized rapidly.

Figure 1: Study area: Volusia County and the Halifax River watershed in central east Florida.

According to the 2022 census, the total population of the watershed considered for this study is about 250,500. Currently, about 74,000 people live in the City of Daytona Beach, with an increase of about 3.8 percent between 2020 and 2021. According to 2019 national land cover data, this watershed is composed of about 29 percent developed land of various kinds. Forest/shrub covers about 17 percent of this watershed with 22 percent wetlands, and 4 percent of hay/pasture/and herbaceous land cover (MRLC, 2022). The rest of it is open water.

Data and Analysis

We carried out population-landcover trend analysis and explored interactions between changing land cover and sea-level-driven coastal inundation. We acquired data and information from the US Census to determine the watershed’s total population and used the population of one of the

major cities in the watershed to explore change in population over time. We then carried out a landcover change analysis using US national land cover data (NLCD) for the years 2001 and 2019 (MRLC, 2022). The multi-resolution land characteristics consortium classifies developed landcover into four different categories: Developed Open Space, Developed Low Intensity, Developed Medium Intensity, and Developed High Intensity. We focused on how different developed land covers have changed over time in the watershed with a special focus on high-density land use. Using ArcGIS Pro 2.8 (ESRI ArcGIS Pro, 2022) we calculated the total area and percentage of various development landcovers from the NLCD dataset. We used Florida 2070 projected developed land cover (Carr and Zwick, 2016) and examined the future change in land cover assumed to be primarily driven by economic development and in-migration to the region. The analysis was performed by calculating the total area as well as the percentage of various developed land cover types in 2001 and 2019 based on NLCD and projected developed landcover in 2070 based on Thousand Friends of Florida's 2070 (Carr and Zwick, 2016) projected land cover using ArcGIS Pro 2.8.

We then examined the risk of flooding in the watershed based on NOAA's sea level rise (SLR) projection(s) for 2100 (NOAA SLR Data, 2022) to forecast how current and projected future development interact with the flooding potential in this urban watershed. We extracted the percentage of flooded developed land within 1-ft SLR and 6-ft SLR by 2100 by employing various geospatial analysis tools in ArcGIS Pro. We first used the Extract function by Attributes tool in ArcGIS Pro to extract various developed land cover types from NLCD Datasets. We then aggregated these different landcover types to one "developed" land cover. We used sea level rise polygons from NOAA to extract the developed landcover and calculated the area of the current developed landcover which would be inundated. For future developed land cover projection polygons, we first converted polygons to a raster format of same cell size as of current developed land cover. We then employed the same method as current developed land cover to extract future landcover using NOAA's SLR projections polygons.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Population and Landcover

The 3.8 percent population increase of Daytona Beach from 2020 to 2021 is significantly higher than both the US national trend (~0.1 %) and Florida trend (1.1%) (US Census Bureau, 2022), suggesting rapid population increase over time in this watershed. As expected, landcover distribution of this watershed has been changing rapidly as well. Our analysis shows that during the

two decades from 2001 to 2019 the area of medium-intensity housing and high-intensity housing almost doubled while the total area of developed open space and low-intensity development remained the same (Figure 2). Developed Open Space is an area with a mixture of constructed materials with predominant coverage of vegetation especially in the form of lawn grasses with less than 20 percent of impervious coverage (MRLC, 2022). Although the area in square kilometers of Developed Open Space and Low Intensity Development remain similar between 2001 and 2019, it does not mean that those are the same locations as in 2001. The Developed Open Space and Low Intensity Development converted to higher intensity development while natural lands were converted to Developed Open Space and Low Intensity Development. That led to areas of lower intensity development in 2001 remaining comparable to 2001 while significantly consuming natural lands and increasing high-density development.

Figure 2: Change in Halifax River watershed landcover between 2001 and 2019. Data source (MRLC, 2022).

The conversion of natural areas into new developments is projected to increase in the future based on the projected trend of population growth and distribution of the population based on our analysis. In 2001 only 237 square kilometers (32%) of the watershed was developed while 273 square kilometers (37%) of the watershed are currently developed, a number projected to increase to about 400 square kilometers (53%) by 2070 (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Developed area coverage in the Halifax River watershed over time (MRLC, 2022; Carr and Zwick, 2016). Notice that the area of developed land is projected to almost double from 2019 to 2070.

The rapid change in area and density of developed land is attributed to both an increase in economic opportunity and the high level of amenities in the region. Both sides of the Halifax River are filled with housing. The coastal area is also fully developed with single-family housing, condominiums, hotels, and businesses. This area is economically vibrant, with Volusia County hosting more than 10 million tourists in 2018 (Abbott, 2022). An analysis of economic development in the Halifax watershed (Ekanayake et. al., 2020) hints at the balance in the region among economic opportunity, natural amenities, and recreational amenities, and finds that the three industries with the best potential for growth are Manufacturing and Construction; Agriculture, Forestry, Fishing, and Hunting; and Accommodation and Food Services. The implication is that each of the factors that makes the Halifax watershed region an attractive area in which to settle are poised for future growth. In addition to the economic opportunity, changes in land cover might also have been driven by the nearest big city, Orlando. Land development in the Halifax watershed accelerated rapidly following the development of Disney World in Orlando in 1971, which is a little over one hour's

drive away. The home of Walt Disney World, Sea World, and Universal Studios, Orlando is one of the most visited cities in Florida, hosting 79.8 million visitors in 2019 (Visit Orlando, 2022).

The Halifax River region is undergoing more rapid change in urban area and density than other parts of Florida. Carr and Zwick (2016), in their analysis of the future of Florida’s land use, point out that the east coast of Florida is one of the regions with dramatic changes in land cover. There is thus an opportunity to conserve land and limit further land development in this watershed in order to maintain biodiversity, ecosystem services, and reduce future flood damage. Urban sprawl can be slowed by setting aside special natural and cultural sites for conservation, supporting greenways and wildlife corridors, incentivizing landowners to conserve important undeveloped or minimally impacted land, and working towards reducing impacts from the new development in the region (Carr and Zwick, 2016). It is possible for the region to increase density in places where development already exists while policymakers attempt to protect undeveloped land.

Future Flooding Vulnerabilities and Landcover

Under the assumption that the current map of developed lands will remain unchanged over the period in which sea level rises (SLR) one foot above current levels, we find that about two square kilometers of currently developed area (0.73%) will be inundated. One of the likeliest projections, often used in resilience planning in this region, is for a one meter of sea level rise by 2100 (ECFRRAP, 2018). When our model elevates sea level to the 6-ft NOAA SLR scenario, over 26 square kilometers (~10 %) of currently developed lands will be inundated (Figures 4 and 5).

Figure 4: Area of current and future vulnerable development in the Halifax River watershed. Data sources: MRLC, 2022; NOAA SLR Data, 2022; Carr and Zwick, 2016

Figure 5: Interaction between current developed land and future sea level rise in the Halifax River watershed. Data sources: MRLC, 2022; NOAA SLR Data, 2022.

Several observations can be made from this initial stage in our analysis. First, in addition to the two square kilometers of existing houses that are likely to be flooded in the next 20 years, this model does not include storm surge, so any large storm will compress the time when these houses are inundated and increase the area of flood risk. While two square kilometers represents less than one percent of all development, houses in these areas will either be protected by additional infrastructure, remodeled to be resistant to flooding, or abandoned. Second, a sea level rise of six

feet will flood significantly more developed land and require substantial additional investments in green infrastructure, built infrastructure, flood mitigation remodeling, and policies designed to retreat from these areas to prevent an enormous loss of housing. While there is some time to initiate these more aggressive mitigation and prevention strategies, the amount of time and resources required must not be underestimated. If flood risks and insurance costs increase while associated amenities are degraded (for example, beach erosion accelerated by the construction of protective sea walls), then the immigration that drives higher housing values and a growing tax base could be affected long before houses are physically inundated. These observations are consistent with other analyses. The East Central Florida Planning Council (ECFRPC, 2017) finds that residential housing makes up approximately 90% of the parcels in Volusia County that will be flooded in an SLR analysis with storm surge. It is interesting that, regardless of the scenario, approximately one third of the houses expected to be inundated are more than 50 years old.

Our second analysis uses land cover forecasts by Carr and Zwick (2016) and overlays those developments with 1 ft and 6 ft NOAA SLR forecasts respectively. We find that the area of inundated development increases substantially, with 5.7 square kilometers inundated under 1 ft SLR and 36.41 sq kilometers inundated under 6 ft SLR (Figures 4 and 6). The sea level rise-induced flooding will impact communities mostly along the Halifax River and its tributaries. Figures 5 and 6 show that the land areas next to tributaries on the north and south side of the watershed have the highest likelihood of being impacted by sea level rise-induced flooding. With land use altered to show new development, the share of housing affected by 1 ft of SLR increases to 1.5% of all housing in the Halifax River watershed, while the size of the inundated areas more than doubles from 2 to 5.7 square kilometers. In the 6 ft SLR scenario, the size of inundated areas increases by roughly 40% from 26 to 36.41 square kilometers. Perhaps the most alarming result of the new development model is that the amount of housing affected by 1 ft of SLR more than doubles. Of the 10.4 kilometers of future construction that will be inundated by 6 ft of SLR, over one-third would be flooded by just 1 ft of SLR. The implication is that time for effective land use planning is short.

Figure 6: Interaction between projected developed land (2070) and future sea level rise (2100) in the Halifax River watershed. Data sources: MRLC, 2022; NOAA SLR Data, 2022; Carr and Zwick, 2016.

By preventing the construction of future developments in areas likely to be inundated by an additional 1 ft of SLR, the region potentially can cut the direct damage costs in half over the next 20 to 30 years. However, simply preventing development in vulnerable areas is a costly sledgehammer approach to the problem. It may be far more effective to incorporate green infrastructure in these areas of likely flooding to reduce the effects of flooding beyond these areas. Parks, swales, and green

roofs not only act as storage areas to prevent water from overwhelming storm water drainage systems, they also lower energy costs, increase natural habitats, offer recreational activities, and increase the value of houses located nearby (EPA, 2014). While green infrastructure can improve the livability of neighborhoods during more severe flood events, SLR will require substantial investments to prevent the incursion of the ocean or, most likely, increased flooding from the Halifax River. Eventually, as SLR approaches 6 ft, it may be too costly to fortify and protect the most flood-prone areas or to maintain the infrastructure that supports those areas.

While these decisions and associated behavioral changes may not be made immediately, they will be required in the very near future and will shape communities' identities in this urban watershed. Will sea walls replace beach activities, resulting in more passive ocean experiences, or will accommodations be put in place to allow beaches to migrate? As infrastructure services in areas that are frequently flooded become increasingly expensive due to frequent upgrades and repairs, how will the community respond? Communities that recognize this reality early can develop a process for temporary use of high-risk areas, combined with a (compensated or uncompensated) planned retreat that fosters natural amenities in flooded areas. These communities will have lower mitigation costs, and will be more attractive to immigrants, residents, and investors looking for a vibrant economy with plentiful amenities to enhance quality of life. Volusia County is aware of this challenge and is actively working on solutions. The County is incorporating climate change effects into its land use planning by prioritizing areas for conservation based on the ecosystem services (natural amenities) offered by different parcels, locations where development could be at high risk of flooding, and areas where green infrastructure could be most effective.

CONCLUSIONS

Global climate change is certainly causing shifts in the tide and storm surge height of the ocean that will directly impact the world's coasts and result in damage to ecosystems, people, and property. The southeast region of the USA will see about 1 ft to 6 ft SLR by 2100 according to a recent NOAA prediction of future sea level rise in the USA. In our work of assessment of sea level rise and inundation potential by 2100, we report that about 2 to 36 square kilometers of the developed land in the area will be inundated under 1 ft and 6 ft sea level rise scenarios, amounting to about 1 to 13 percent of currently developed land respectively. It is worth mentioning that the area

we analyzed utilizes current and future developed land only and does not include other landcover types.

The Halifax urban watershed is undergoing rapid changes in population and developed land cover driven by economic opportunity locally and regionally. About 37 percent of the watershed is already developed and is further projected to be more than 53 percent developed by 2070. If the trajectory continues, it will significantly reduce natural habitat, biodiversity, and the means for flood control. Sea level rise-induced flooding will significantly impact development and the region's economy. There is an opportunity to conserve land and control further growth in this watershed in order to maintain biodiversity and ecosystem services and limit future flood damage. The stakeholders in the region can avoid the worst consequences of future SLR by planning for development outside of the flood prone areas, increasing density of the current developed areas to avoid the expansions, and setting area aside for land and water conservation.

LIMITATIONS

In this work we focused on Volusia County rather than the entire watershed of the Halifax River. A small area of the watershed extends into Flagler County as well, but we have not examined new adaptation options and people's tendency to retreat after the major flooding events there. If new adaptations to sea level rise are applied in this area, the potential loss of developed land could be reduced. This will have major impacts in the new development and housing markets which we did not evaluate because of the lack of anticipatory adaptation data at the watershed scale. We also have not analyzed the economic capacity of the communities in that region. Although we consider housing prices as one of the major factors in relation to new development and sea level rise-induced flooding, in this work we were not able to run direct analysis by relating those variables because of temporal mismatch in the data available in the public domain. Nonetheless, we were able to present empirical evidence of current and future trends of socio-economy driven landcover changes and their interactions with climate change driven coastal flooding in this part of East Central Florida.

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Epilogue: Transportation, Development, and the Landscape of the Halifax Region

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The previous articles in this edition have painted a relatively broad picture of the development of the Halifax River region highlighting transportation, access, and consequent activities. It seems clear that the external immigration, occupation, and development of the Halifax River watershed was tightly linked to the expansion of access to the area, access that was both aided and hindered by the physical geography of the region. As external technology and effort were focused on the area, the impacts of that effort accrued to the detriment of some groups (such as the original populations at the time of outside arrivals) or activities (such as indigo and sugar agriculture) and to the benefit of others (e.g. recreation, urbanization). Underlying the extensive early changes to the region, however, was a common theme: the need to first conform with, adapt to, or otherwise alter the restrictions on movement imposed by the surrounding landscape.

One of the more interesting patterns common to the previous chapters is the early importance of directionality imposed by the landscape. The predominant alignment of features such as ridges and troughs from ancient shorelines, rivers, and the coastline is (relatively and generally speaking) north-south (N/S), which influenced early access into the region. Centuries ago, the easiest ways to enter the region were via the Halifax River (and to the west the St. Johns River) and the coast, with later land movement (such as along the King's Highway) largely following the N/S ridge and trough alignment. Movement in this direction conformed to the landscape and was thus relatively easy when compared to movement along an east-west axis, which required travel through less developed, less easily traversed areas. Thus, early on, major influences in the area were more likely to enter the Halifax River region from the north or even Europe than from the Gulf of Mexico or western US, while the native populations had to deal with shared or even lost access to these more efficient travel corridors and the potential to be squeezed into lands between them.

The difficulties with movement in the area from the 1500s through the 1700s led to a rather piecemeal development pattern as people tried to create new settlements in areas where other people

had already settled, to obtain resources in places where they were already claimed (or did not yet exist) and were hard to protect, and to generate stable profit in areas that were not particularly stable. Florida's written history is replete with stories of conflicts won and lost, locations changing hands peacefully or not, agreements made and broken, settlements appearing and disappearing, and businesses begun and lost, a great deal of it tied directly or indirectly to exploration, recreation, and settlement opportunities for the wealthy (or hopefully-to-be-wealthy). Impacts from the settlements and their associated agriculture and lumber operations almost certainly had an ecological impact on the surrounding landscape, but the combination of the scattered spatial and temporal nature of those early efforts, the difficulties with transportation of goods and people, the disagreements with the existing inhabitants, and the challenging and dynamic ecological nature of the landscape have contributed to relatively few visible signs of those early impacts to be found today. Indeed, while there are limited records of environmental impacts from early written history in Florida, the environmental impacts of modern activities in the Halifax River urban watershed would almost certainly overshadow them.

Overlain with these impacts over time was a concurrent advance in technology. From coastal vessels and river junket boats to railways, highways, and airports, increases in the convenience and efficiency of transportation slowly overcame the early limitations on access from outside, improving the probability of successful development and settlement efforts despite the attempts by existing populations to either prevent it or coexist with it (creating an ever-evolving list of social winners and losers). Today, with exceptions for transportation regulations, modern transportation methods have all but eliminated the directional and ground cover restrictions of the early movement through the region. Ironically, though, much of the region's current development and economic activity is still associated with aspects of settlement (e.g. new housing developments), exploration (e.g. retirees and vacationers coming to experience the region), or recreation (e.g. boating and NASCAR-associated activity). In the area, you can still see remnants of the old pattern of initial settlement locations along the more accessible routes, several of which have grown over time, followed by expansion into some of the intervening land as technology and circumstance permitted.

The result of minimization of barriers to access is a region of significant urbanization, modernization, and economic development. Expansion in these areas has become detached from earlier tendencies toward N/S directionality, as considerable development is expanding to the west, away from the Halifax River and coastline. While minimization of barriers has eliminated several of

the past concerns regarding survival in the area, the advances have come with their own costs. Effectively the entire Halifax River watershed has been modified by human activities ranging from resource management to elimination of habitats for development. The old trails and river boats have been replaced by modern highways and air traffic that allow access to the area for both long-term and short-term activity, resulting in an ever-changing but nonetheless growing population with its expanding environmental impacts from air pollution, chemicals, and urban runoff, impacts that could not have been imagined by the original occupants of the area. In another irony, stress on the area and its habitats from human activity is such that the old river and beach shores, once defining the most effective means of access, are now directly and indirectly impacted up to the point of degradation despite the expanded routes of access.

Instead, people are inhabiting what was once marsh, swamp, beach and dune, forest, and even agricultural land, and with that access comes more impact, development, and habitat alteration. Being a coastal watershed, the Halifax already has a number of challenges to long-term sustainability in the form of storm frequency, coastal flooding, saltwater intrusion, and harmful algal blooms among others; challenges that are expected to worsen with climate change. Indeed, climate change could potentially produce the greatest irony of all: a sort of reversal of the ease of access and development that occurred in the region. While historically the coastline was a major access and development point for the Halifax River and environs, expected sea level rise due to climate change can be expected to make our present coastal infrastructure far less stable. Already an issue in the Halifax River region and elsewhere, coastal flooding associated with the combination of storms and sea level rise is expected to exacerbate already damaging events over much of low-lying coastal Florida, forcing the population to make a choice to either attempt to fight against these environmental forces or to retreat from their impacts into more stable areas currently further inland. (The fact that much of this climate change can be linked to our recent expanding development and technological activity adds an interesting grace note to the situation.) Given these expected changing drivers to environmental impacts, the desire to maintain a sustainable coastal system should encourage us to be particularly vigilant when it comes to the intensity of environmental impacts that are under our near-term control, as are many of the things discussed in this issue.

We certainly have settlements and economic activity in the Halifax River watershed now, but there is no doubt about the environmental and social costs that have come with it. The connections are enough that we might want to consider what it will mean for the region if we continue to create

more access, economic activity, and opportunity for recreation in what's left of the original habitats of the area. Perhaps it is time to consider how much environmental impact has already occurred in the Halifax area, how much more is likely to occur in the coming years, and how to address the negative social impacts that occur along the way as best we can. In particular, we may want to consider how much more ease of access and activity the region can actually support, and whether our planning in that regard is doing justice to the environment as well as all who would be affected today and in the future.